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Title: SEA-LEVEL RISE AND ANTHROPOGENIC ACTIVITIES RECORDED IN THE LATE
PLEISTOCENE/HOLOCENE SEDIMENTARY INFILL OF THE GUADIANA ESTUARY (SW IBERIA)

Article Type: Research and Review Paper

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Pyrite Belt

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Abstract: This study reviews data on sea-level rise during the last 13000yr cal. BP (13kyr) as recorded in the estuarine sediments of the Guadiana River (SE Portugal, SW Spain). We combined new data from a 63m-long borehole, drilled through the entire postglacial sedimentary sequence, with information on five previously studied cores. By integrating sedimentological, geochemical and palaeontological proxies, we were able to make a palaeoenvironmental reconstruction of the Guadiana terminal palaeovalley during the last 13kyr and propose a curve of sea-level rise for the SW Iberian Atlantic margin. Our foraminifera-based palaeoecological reconstruction, anchored to a ^{14}C age model, reveals rapid sea-level rise from 13kyr, interrupted during the Younger Dryas and resuming ca 11.5kyr. The pace of marine transgression slackened ca. 7.5kyr and since then has progressed upwards at a rate of $1.2\text{mm}\cdot\text{yr}^{-1}$.

Holocene-Anthropocene sediments from two boreholes were also analysed to assess the timing, levels and sources of trace metals produced by acid mine drainage from the Iberian Pyrite Belt. Study of metal/aluminium ratios through the profiles allowed background metal concentrations to be estimated from lithostratigraphic units older than ca. 5kyr (i.e. unaffected by anthropogenic activities). Human activities are especially evident from 4.5kyr (the beginning of the Copper Age), with anthropogenic sources of metal fluxes prevailing over natural sources (especially Pb, Co, Ni, and Mn, and, to a lesser extent, Zn, Cu, and Ni). Mining activities became particularly intensive between the late Bronze Age and the Roman period (3-1.5kyr), when the highest metal enrichment factors were recorded: $\text{EFPb} \approx 2$, $\text{EFCd} > 10$, $\text{EFCr} \approx 2$, $\text{EFCu} \approx 3$, $\text{EFZn} = 1.4$. This study reveals the utility of postglacial sedimentary records for reconstructing historical changes in regional water-sediment quality and separating natural and anthropogenic sources of geochemical contaminants.

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Huelva, June 24, 2011

Dear Editor of Quaternary Science Reviews,

I am pleased to submit the manuscript entitled: **“SEA-LEVEL RISE AND ANTHROPOGENIC ACTIVITIES RECORDED IN THE POSTGLACIAL SEDIMENTARY INFILL OF THE GUADIANA ESTUARY (SW IBERIA)”**, which is submitted for its consideration to publication in **Quaternary Science Reviews**.

The present study has the aim to integrate the information on geochemical and sedimentary evolution of the Guadiana Estuary (SW Iberia) and to propose a curve for the accompanying postglacial sea level rise in the SW Iberian which embraces the terminal Pleistocene and Holocene. In addition, our goal will be to establish background values for contaminant elements, discriminating between natural and anthropogenic inputs of these elements into this ecosystem affected by Acid Mine Drainage (AMD). This is expected to reveal relationships between the sedimentary evolution of the estuary and the distribution of paleo-markers in its record.

This fulfils publication requirements for the following reasons, which are perfectly adjusted to the request of the journal:

1. The manuscript established the postglacial sea-level rise of the Guadiana Estuary and for extension in the SW Iberian Peninsula.
2. The work present new result on the reconstruction of the history of anthropogenic impacts on natural ecosystems based on geochemical paleo-markers. These data provide critical reviews of other previously published data indicating that this estuary could be considered as a non polluted

environmental system. So, the results support the recent work in the Guadiana Estuary and demonstrate that this estuarine system, considered historically as a non-contaminated environment, is being certainly affected by historical mining activities.

3. The results show the used of sedimentological-geochemical markers in sedimentary record with a powerful tool to historical reconstructions and the discrimination between natural or anthropogenic inputs of the principal metals and metalloid responsible to pollution on the estuarine ecosystems.

Hope you will consider our manuscript for publication in your journal.

Yours sincerely,

Joaquín Delgado.

Dear Colin Murray-Wallace Editor-in-Chief of Quaternary Science Reviews,

We have corrected the mistypes and made all suggested changes on the revised manuscript following your comments (when applicable, see below). We really appreciate again the time that reviewers and editor have invested in improving our paper.

Below we have included a detailed answer to all specific comments of the reviewers and our response to each one (in bold type).

Yours sincerely,

J. Delgado and T. Boski.-

Reviewer #1: SEA-LEVEL RISE AND ANTHROPOGENIC ACTIVITIES RECORDED IN THE POSTGLACIAL SEDIMENTARY INFILL OF THE GUADIANA ESTUARY (SW IBERIA)

Manuscript Number JQSR-D-11-00235

Delgado et al.

Comments

This paper presents some interesting new micropalaeontological and geochemical data from a large estuarine infill in southern Portugal, which are shown to have a bearing on local/regional reconstructions of postglacial sea-level change and human occupation. The geochemical data in particular provide some significant insights into the imprint of land clearance, mining and other human activities on the regional sedimentary record. The new sea-level data presented are largely discussed in the context of data from a previously described local core; the results add some new perspectives, although there is little attempt to consider the wider significance of the data in the context of late-glacial and Holocene RSL records from elsewhere in Europe or further afield - perhaps because this has been done elsewhere?

Response: Yes, more global context and relations between SLR and human occupation, with new references, were added to the discussion section.

Whilst there are several elements of the paper that would certainly appeal to readers of QSR (the sea-level data; the methodological approaches used to detect patterns of catchment disturbance during the last few millennia), other aspects are not strongly in line with the common themes of a Quaternary Science journal (e.g. some aspects of the elemental chemistry - these might arguably be better suited to a sedimentary geology or geochemistry journal). To justify the inclusion of some these data / discussions in this journal, I would have liked to have seen stronger links between the two halves of the study (the sea-level and palaeoenvironmental history section and the geochemical study), which don't always fit well together (at times the manuscript has the feel of two papers joined together, not one).

Response: A cause-effect relationship between sea-level rise and geochemical fluxes into and out of the estuary is not at all a straightforward relation. Therefore our aim here is more modest, i.e. to bring together two processes with a common timescale. Nevertheless we pointed out several lines of geochemical/elemental evidence for the above relationship e.g. Fe, Sr and As. What is certainly much more meaningful is the record of anthropogenic impacts in the river basin, which was very well documented.

A clearer explanation of the wider significance of the study in the 'Introduction' and stronger linking between the sections would go a long way towards achieving this and strengthening the appeal to a 'Quaternary science' audience. For example, more could be made of the changing depositional context and provenance of the sediments reported in Section 3.1.2 on the geochemical data presented in Section 3.2.3 (e.g., there's no mention of the potential impacts of a change from intertidal to floodplain sedimentation on the metal data for core CM6 or the possible impacts of re-working in an intertidal environment on these data..).

Response: We agree with this suggestion, and we added references and additional text that make a stronger link between the Holocene stabilization of the sea level and changes in the patterns of human occupation; moreover, the paragraph in the Introduction chapter was re-written.

Brief consideration of the potential impact of metal contamination on the foraminiferal assemblages might also be given in Section 3.1 (presumably no influence was picked up?) A fall in foraminiferal concentrations in the upper part of the sequence might reflect this. There could also be some discussion on the insights that might be gained from the geochemistry data for inferring accretion rate changes? (and hence SL rise estimates?) - these points would all provide scope for stronger cohesion between different elements of the paper.

Response: The observed concentration levels of the analysed heavy metals with are too low to affect the foraminifera. We are more inclined to attribute the variation in abundance of foraminifera to diagenetic processes occurring in the sediment.

Otherwise the structure of the paper is generally sound, although the language, grammar and spelling need attention in many places (please see extensive comments on the attached pdf). Some sections could also be written more succinctly.

Specific points:

1. The 'Highlights' would benefit from re-phrasing - these read like a list of titles - a few more linking words would be helpful.

Response: The Highlights have been rephrased according with the reviewer's suggestion.

2. As stated above, the sea-level history section would benefit from further discussion on the regional / international significance of the data (e.g. more emphasis on the acquisition of data from the late-glacial period, and the significance for better understanding rapid early Holocene RSL rise?). Brief reference could be made to the key paper published recently by Hijma & Cohen around 8.2 K from the Netherlands in 'Geology' for example (see pdf for details)

Response: The discussion was broadened and references added

3. The foraminiferal data sections (3.1.1.1 and 3.1.1.2) include some omissions and minor inaccuracies. Please see comments on pdf.

Re: Done.

4. The foraminiferal data aren't presented in a figure or table - a diagram or at the very least a Supplementary table should be included as these data form a key part of the interpretations.

Response: We added more graphical information on benthic foram assembly structure. The values of FIMI (Foraminiferal Index of Marine Influence) was added to the lithological column plot, together with pie-chart diagrams for CM6 (CM5 was discussed in detail in our previous paper) showing the proportions of dominant foraminifera species.

5. The diatom data are rather insubstantial - if a fuller dataset is available this should be tabulated. There's also no mention of how many valves were counted per sample.

Response: We added the information about the counting procedure of diatom frustules in methodology section and expanded the diatom-based identification of sedimentary environment in sections 3.1.1.1 and 3.1.1.2.

6. Mention is made on p. 11 of marine deposits of potential MIS 5e (substage 5e?) age near the base of borehole CM6. The regional distribution and foraminiferal biostratigraphy of these sediments needs to be discussed more fully. Also, were samples from this unit examined geochemically and if so what was the significance?

Response: The hypothetical mention of MIS 5e was re-written, although it may be put only as a supposition because there are no described deposits of that age from the Iberian Continental Margin. However, the strength of the marine imprint is more in favour of MIS 5e than 3.

7. pp. 12-13: The error terms discussed on the sea-level data points require clearer and fuller explanation - the text is difficult to follow here.

Response: The text sections annotated by the reviewer were re-written.

8. pp. 13, paragraph 2: more caution needs to be given in interpreting the inferred rates of SL rise given the low number of samples dated, vertical errors and the problems with the material dated.

Response: Yes, this was addressed according to the indications in the text

9. pp. 13, paragraph 2: changes in accommodation space are also only one factor influencing accretion rates - a wider appraisal of the complexities of estuarine dynamics/sedimentation would be helpful here.

Response: Certainly the accommodation space is not the only factor influencing accumulation rates. However it is certainly the main factor, together with tidal transport of shelf sediments entering into the estuary. We added this second factor to the discussion.

10. pp. 20: an important link is made here between metal enrichment and the Holocene climatic optima but there's no attempt to explain the processes - this needs a fuller explanation.

Response: The paragraph has been re-written in order to explain the link between metal enrichment and the climate optimum.

11. Referencing - this is generally good, although some more up-to-date references would be helpful in the sea-level section (see pdf).

Response: We added many new references in the sections where the discussion was broadened.

12. pp. 22 - explain in the main body of the text what is meant by 'Modern times'. In this paragraph (starting line 808) the discussion also seems out of order (surficial sediment/modern data are discussed first, then the discussion goes back to Medieval times).

Response: To explain what we mean by "Modern Times", the discussion from the Medieval Period to recent times has been re-written and chronologically ordered according to the reviewer's suggestion. Also, the time intervals have been included in the new version of the manuscript.

13. **Table 2:** reference is made here to several mollusc specimens that were dated - the species names need to be given in full if they haven't previously been mentioned in the text.

Response: We changed or included full species names as suggested by the reviewer.

14. **Figure 1:** shading, symbols and labels on this map could be improved

Response: We agree. The figure has been improved. Additionally, we have included a colour figure for the web publication.

15. **Figure 3:** why were no error bars plotted on the sea-level data points on Fig A like on Fig B?

Response: In the new version of the manuscript the figures have been separated. We have added the error bars in Fig. 4. Moreover in the figure of sea-level rise (Fig. 5) we have not used the actual depth of the samples from channel facies but the corrected value for the mean depth of the main estuarine channel.

16. **Figures 7 and 8:** some of the labels (for depths particularly) need to be enlarged - when scaled down for publication it will be difficult to read these

Response: According to reviewer's annotations (in this line and the .pdf notes) labels and legends of the figures 6, 7 and 8 have been enlarged for ease of reading.

Other:

There are a large number of minor grammatical, punctuation errors and inconsistencies in the formatting (please see 'sticky' notes on the pdf).
E.g.

+commas are missing for the references presented in brackets in the text (checkjournal format for QSR (e.g. Goy et al.,[missing comma?] 1996; Dabrio et al., 2000).

+Different use of spaces for units e.g. 20 m; 20m; 20-m etc - consistency needed

+Indentation for paragraphs is inconsistent; sections with multiple subsections need to be delimited with spaces

+'Metres' is spelt differently in different places (metres v meters)

+ 'Palleovalleys / palleoenvironmental' - mis-spelt throughout

+ 'Sea-level rise' - hyphen is used inconsistently

The text needs to be checked throughout.

Response: All errors pointed by the reviewer were checked in terms of grammar, use of units, indentation for paragraphs and use of English and revised in detail.

Other comments to several annotations of reviewer 1.

The remaining text annotations were corrected according to the suggestions.

Reviewer#1

Line 200 - " is an international notation for inch

Line 282 - separation of foraminifera for sampling is according to Scott and Hermelin (1993) cited in the next sentence.

Line 339 - Trochammina is indeed a high saltmarsh species.

Line 341 - Scavenging refers to mineral phases (in the sense of chemical adsorption) and not to foraminifera.

Line 352 - *Haynesina germanica* is very widely used, dominant term. We do not think that considerations on taxonomic terminology are appropriate in the section dealing with the description of sedimentary units.

Line 415 - Yes.

Line 441 - the term "borehole mouth" means borehole opening and is a widely used term. Both openings were protected by a casing tube whose top was above the ground in order to avoid submergence during the spring tide. 20cm is the error margin (see methodology) in estimating the vertical position of borehole opening with respect to spring high water (SHW).

Line 445 - we take the highest value of the main tidal channel depth. The boreholes were drilled in the proximity of the main channel, which may not have migrated too much in the past because of structural (narrowness) constraints.

Line 481 - we used the term sea surface instead of mean sea level in order to not repeat the same words too many times.

Line 491 - Indeed catchment disturbance through changing vegetation cover and/or forest clearing is a modulator of sediment delivery from the estuary to shelf. However the sediment may only accumulate where space exists for it. If this space is insufficient within the inner estuary, a deltaic system will build up.

Reviewer #2:

I found this paper to be well written and well illustrated. Whilst I am not as knowledgeable as I would like to be on the chemistry of estuarine sediments, I found the sea level information to be of interest. My comments are divided into two sections. In the first, I comment on the spelling, grammar and syntax; in the second I comment on the science.

1. Use of English.

Highlights: "...SW Iberian peninsula." (i.e. complete the sentence)

delete "palleo-reconstruction" replace with "palaeo-reconstruction"

delete "Palleo-markers" replace with "palaeo-markers"

"...SW Iberian peninsula." (i.e. complete the sentence).

Line 263 delete "micropalleontological" replace with "micropalaeontological"

Line 441 delete "mouth" replace with "top"

Lines 817, 846, 860 delete "palleoenvironmental" replace with "palaeoenvironmental"

Response: The highlights and spelling have been corrected considering these annotations and those of reviewer#1. "Borehole mouth" is a drilling term in current use.

2. Science.

This paper reads like an account of sediment geochemistry, with the sea level element being only one aspect. Hence the title "Evidence of anthropogenic activities and sea-level rise from the sedimentary infill of the Guadiana estuary in South West Iberia" would seem better to me.

Response: We added a more precise stratigraphic meaning to the title but we would like to maintain the rest of original

because, after 2 previously published papers, the present goes beyond mere recognition of sea-level rise and proposes the first regional curve of sea-level rise based on a critical review of previous data and the addition of new ones.

On the matter of terminology and definitions, I should like to see at the end of "Introduction" an explanation of what the authors mean by "postglacial" and what they understand to be the "Holocene" (and why).

"Postglacial" is sometimes used as a specific term and sometimes as a general statement of a period of time after deglaciation. In northern Europe and North America, the Holocene is well defined as the time after the Younger Dryas, i.e. after 11,650 cal. BP (for example see Smith et al., QSR 2011). In some other parts of the world, generally where the Younger Dryas is not recognised, a longer period is implied in accounts. In this paper, the authors seem to include the Younger Dryas in the Holocene (e.g. lines 474, 680). Accounts such as those of Rasmussen et al. (J. Geophys. Res. 2006) and Walker et al. (J. Quat. Sci., 2009) clearly define the Holocene as after the Younger Dryas.

Response: The meaning of postglacial embraces the whole period after the LGM, including the terminal Pleistocene and the Holocene. The use of the term Holocene as an alternative to Post-glacial has been corrected in the manuscript. We added this information to the introduction and changed the title of the paper accordingly.

The authors should be more circumspect about their interpretation of the evidence for sea level change. For example, the dating of the wood fragment (line 390) is not necessarily an accurate indication of sea level rise at that point, since it was derived.

The evidence from the mollusc dates (e.g. lines 431 et seq.) may be more general given the habitat ranges of the species, although the foraminifera dates are more reliable.

Response: We incorporated more reserve into several affirmations

I would have preferred the calibrated ages to have been given to 2 SD (Table 2), and in the text the mid point dates given to be stated as such (e.g. lines 389, 390). However, although one can "pick holes" in the sea level dates, the results are most interesting and the observation of a marked change in the sea level rise around 7800 BP is in line with observations of eustatic changes elsewhere, and of modelled work (e.g. Milne et al., QSR 2005).

Concerning the issue of the effect of the Lake Agassiz-Ojibway melt water pulse, I draw the attention of the authors to papers by Bird et al. (Geology, 2010), Tornqvist et al. (Geophysical research Letters, 2004) and Hijma and Cohen (Geology, 2010). However, the event may not have been the last pulse from the Laurentide IceSheet, see Smith et al., QSR 2011.

Response: We changed the calibration from 1 SD to 2 SD as suggested. The new references were added.

Reviewer #3:

I have now had a chance to read the ms of Delgado et al. "SEA-LEVEL RISE AND ANTHROPOGENIC ACTIVITIES RECORDED IN THE POSTGLACIAL SEDIMENTARY INFILL OF THE GUADIANA ESTUARY (SW IBERIA)" in which they present sediment core records of paleovalley infill of an estuary on the Portuguese/Spain border. The ms is reasonably well written and presented, however, I am not so convinced it is an ideal fit with QSR primarily because of its regional vs global significance (they do derive a sea level curve but fail to compare it to other curves and comment on the agreement) and the focus on metal contamination although interesting, I felt might be more appropriate in an environmental geochemistry journal such as Applied Geochemistry. At any rate, if you decide it is appropriate for QSR then I have no problem with it being published once the concerns below are addressed to your satisfaction.

Response: More context was given to the sea-level curve. Comparisons with other Iberian and world studies were made.

The records they present are most welcome as such valley fill deposits, although commonly observed in seismic profiles for example, are rarely studied in terms of their depositional history. One of the major outcomes of their study is a sea level curve which I believe is generally well documented and the limits are explained. I do think that one of the challenges in deriving sea level in their estuary is the fairly large amplitude tide of 2.8 m. This translates into a large area being within the estuary facies domain and makes it difficult to pin down elevation relative to MSL.

I wondered if they recorded any evidence of periodic subaerial exposure in the core (mudcracks, oxidation fronts, etc)?

Response: No, we did not find that kind of structure in the 2 cores. They were observed in the previously described borehole CM4, which was not used as a source of the index points in this study.

As mentioned, I felt they should have done more in the Discussion on how their sea-level curve compares to others they mention.

Also, I feel that they need to address the far field effects of postglacial rebound which is not mentioned at all (the references to far field impacts and an example of a Holocene sea level curve can be found in Compton (2001) (Holocene sea-level fluctuations inferred from the evolution of depositional environments of the southern Langebaan Lagoon salt marsh, South Africa. The Holocene 11, 395-405) and Compton (2006) (The mid-Holocene sea-level highstand at Bogenfels Pan on the southwest coast of Namibia. Quaternary Research 66, 303-310.) Which they may want to have a look at. What about assumptions of sediment supply rate to their core sites?

I take it, they assume supply equalled the rate of accommodation space as a result of rise in sea level, but perhaps this was not always the case depending on paleoclimate variations (rainfall)?

Response: Yes indeed, we assume that that the sedimentation rate kept pace with created accommodation space because we did not observe any hiatuses and/or erosion surfaces in our profiles. This is especially true for the first, rapid sea-level-rise period until ca 8000 ka. The quality of the SLR regression fit further corroborates this assumption. In the upper portion of both profiles, apart from the channel event in the upper part of profile CM6, the creation of accommodation space for both terrigenous and shelf sediments is much slower. This led to the export of sediment and the build up of the Guadiana delta. Consequently, after the Mid Holocene stabilization of SL, the sedimentation record is more patchy and more laterally variable, i.e. less linear in terms of regression. The suggested paper of Compton (2001) analyses the sea-level record in the salt marshes of the Langebaan coastal lagoon in S. Africa after the Holocene stabilization of the SL, i.e. when local sedimentary conditions prevail over eustatically driven processes of deposition. Both the hydrographic setting and the sedimentary dynamics of this site are very different from those analysed in our study, e.g. there is no fluvial input into the Langebaan, therefore the two sites are hardly comparable.

I found the trace metal Discussion fascinating particularly in respect of historical events. However, I was not really convinced given the relative few radiocarbon ages and the uncertainty in these ages that they could make many

of the statements they do. I just wasn't convinced that they had an age resolution to support many of their statements. My other concern about the trace metal work is the possibility of post core recovery oxidation of the fine grained sulphides in the sediment, particularly in the drying out stage of the wet sediment (see for example: Mallinson, D. J., and J. S. Compton. 1998. The influence of iron sulfide oxidation on the sulfur isotope analysis of Miocene phosphorites from Florida, USA. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* 62, 3689-3694). Sulphides can oxidize very rapidly if wet samples are exposed to air and the results are usually seen in the acid leaching of any carbonate samples in the core, something we struggle to control in organic-rich cores. They do mention intervals with evidence for leaching and I wonder if they have considered that it may have occurred after core recovery?

Response: The diagenetic oxidation processes of pyrite described in unit-3 are based on observations and SEM analysis reported by Boski et al. (2008), where the precipitation of carbonate minerals occurs. These carbonates present a clear zonation that corresponds to changes in the proportions between the Fe, Ca, Mg and Mn carbonate system, indicative of slow mineral precipitation in the presence of groundwater circulation.

Moreover, the statistical analysis developed in this work highlights the mineral association found by Boski et al. (2008), which confirms that this process should occur during the diagenesis.

Even though the authors cannot discount a small amount of post core-recovery oxidation, the exposure time was too short to produce the kind of processes suggested by the reviewer. Anyway, in several horizons we complemented the foraminifera observations with diatoms, which are less sensitive to acidity. Additionally, the methodology devised for chemical purposes is widely extended in the geochemical studies of sediments.

The text concerning this question has been re-written to improve comprehension.

Also, the variations pre-human are quite large for some metals and seemed to overlap to quite an extent with the anthropogenic interval near the top of the cores making it perhaps less obvious how much variation is natural vs human induced.

Response: Please note that for a better interpretation of the results, the M/Al palaeo-marker has been normalised with respect

to background values. For this reason, the discussion about the metal sedimentary record is based on EF calculations. The EFs, as defined in section 3.2.4, were calculated taking into account the natural concentrations of metals inferred from the background levels (approx. 8000-10000yr cal. BP), minimising the overlap mentioned by the referee. Figure 10 shows that the possible pre-human EF variations induced by natural changes (i.e. Holocene Climate-optimum) are almost negligible compared to other units where the human activities are widely documented (e.g., 4500yr cal. BP to present). Additionally, we compare the EFs with respect to the temperature and precipitation anomalies during the last 2500 year (new in Fig. 10), and we confirm that the metal fluxes are preferentially controlled by the human occupation and their associated activities (see new version of the manuscript). The relation, when exists, between these parameters and the metal EFs is clearly related to a climate optimum, which favours the civilizations develop, increasing the fluxes of elements such as Co, Cr and Ni. Besides, contrary to what Pp and T^a anomalies could suggest, during two moments of the civilizations decline (late Iron Age and post-Roman migration period) the EFs of these elements decrease to natural concentrations (see Fig. 10), supporting the low influence of these climatic factors on the metal fluxes.

Although generally well written, I did note some errors, for example:

Paleo is not with two ls

Line 161 'destructive'? drilling

Line 324 Planktonic

391 Saltmarsh

393 totally x 2

Table 1 obtained, no data

Response: Corrections were done

Strat column: I would have liked to see more of the micro (foram) and mollusc fossil evidence shown here.

Response: We added that information

Highlights

We reproduce the postglacial-Holocene sea-level rise in the SW Iberian Peninsula.

The sedimentological palaeo-reconstruction is based on foraminifera and ^{14}C Dating.

Geochemical palaeo-markers have distinguished natural and anthropogenic metal sources.

We prove the mine-related pollution during the last 5kyr in the SW Iberian Peninsula.

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SEA-LEVEL RISE AND ANTHROPOGENIC ACTIVITIES RECORDED IN THE LATE
PLEISTOCENE/HOLOCENE SEDIMENTARY INFILL OF THE GUADIANA ESTUARY (SW
IBERIA)

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48 ABSTRACT

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50 This study reviews data on sea-level rise during the last 13000yr cal. BP (13kyr) as recorded in
51 the estuarine sediments of the Guadiana River (SE Portugal, SW Spain). We combined new data
52 from a 63m-long borehole, drilled through the entire postglacial sedimentary sequence, with
53 information on five previously studied cores. By integrating sedimentological, geochemical and
54 palaeontological proxies, we were able to make a palaeoenvironmental reconstruction of the
55 Guadiana terminal palaeovalley during the last 13kyr and propose a curve of sea-level rise for
56 the SW Iberian Atlantic margin. Our foraminifera-based palaeoecological reconstruction,
57 anchored to a ¹⁴C age model, reveals rapid sea-level rise from 13kyr, interrupted during the
58 Younger Dryas and resuming ca 11.5kyr. The pace of marine transgression slackened ca. 7.5kyr
59 and since then has progressed upwards at a rate of 1.2mm·yr⁻¹.

60 Holocene-Anthropocene sediments from two boreholes were also analysed to assess the timing,
61 levels and sources of trace metals produced by acid mine drainage from the Iberian Pyrite Belt.
62 Study of metal/aluminium ratios through the profiles allowed background metal concentrations
63 to be estimated from lithostratigraphic units older than ca. 5kyr (i.e. unaffected by
64 anthropogenic activities). Human activities are especially evident from 4.5kyr (the beginning of
65 the Copper Age), with anthropogenic sources of metal fluxes prevailing over natural sources
66 (especially Pb, Co, Ni, and Mn, and, to a lesser extent, Zn, Cu, and Ni). Mining activities
67 became particularly intensive between the late Bronze Age and the Roman period (3–1.5kyr),
68 when the highest metal enrichment factors were recorded: $EF_{Pb} \approx 2$, $EF_{Cd} > 10$, $EF_{Cr} \approx 2$, $EF_{Cu} \approx$
69 3 , $EF_{Zn} = 1.4$. This study reveals the utility of postglacial sedimentary records for
70 reconstructing historical changes in regional water-sediment quality and separating natural and
71 anthropogenic sources of geochemical contaminants.

72

73 **Keywords:** Late Pleistocene; Holocene; sea-level rise; geochemical record; Guadiana Estuary; Iberian Pyrite Belt.

74

75

76 **1. Introduction**

77

78 The rapid rise in sea-level that occurred following the last glacial maximum (LGM)
79 created tens of metres of vertical accommodation space for sediments deposited in fluvial
80 palaeovalleys. In particular, the deeply incised terminal segments of river valleys provide
81 excellent conditions for the uninterrupted accumulation and preservation of continuous records
82 of sedimentation, evolving progressively from fluvial to estuarine/marine. Estuarine
83 sedimentary archives usually contain abundant ¹⁴C-datable items and may be seen as
84 complementary to the classical, coral-based records used in sea-level reconstructions, like those
85 in Barbados (Fairbanks, 1989) and Tahiti (Bard, 1996, Bard et al. 2010). On the Spanish side of
86 Gulf of Cadiz, the process of postglacial coastal sedimentation has been reviewed by several
87 authors (e.g. Goy et al., 1996; Dabrio et al., 2000; Zazo et al., 2007). Postglacial sea-level rise
88 also induced changes in human settlement patterns (Turney and Brown, 2007), and adaptations
89 to marine transgression (Rolet et al., 2011) through differentiated dispersal patterns and social
90 structures (Fa, 2008). Marine resources made an important contribution to the human diet,
91 especially after 10kyr when terrestrial resources became depleted due to overpopulation (Cohen,
92 1977). The importance of marine resources in the Mesolithic diet has been demonstrated
93 through the isotopic composition of bones (e.g., Fischer et al., 2007; Mannino and Thomas,
94 2001). Considering the limitations on the transport and preservation of food, humans probably
95 spent large amounts of time near the coast (Fischer et al., 2007). Between 8500 and 5630 years
96 cal. BC, a marine diet composed mainly of species occurring on intertidal rocky substrates
97 sustained Mesolithic populations along the SW Portuguese coast (Dean et al., 2011). Shell
98 middens, some of them including artefacts dated to 8-7ka BP, reflect the vital importance of
99 marine sources for pre-historic communities (Bailey and Flemming, 2008) and can be used as a
100 proxy for coastline evolution (e.g., Pavlopoulos et al., 2010).

101 Due to strong chemical gradients and dynamic mixing of continental and marine waters,
102 estuaries have a great capacity for the accumulation of contaminant elements introduced by
103 anthropogenic activities, both within the catchment and the estuary itself (Weistein, 1996;
104 Sanger et al., 1999; Spencer et al., 2003). Since these areas are often places of intense human
105 and animal activity, playing an important role in the maintenance of ecological diversity
106 through their provision of shelter and food to numerous species, contamination levels are of
107 particular interest in estuarine environments (Rae, 1997; Price et al., 2005). Over millennia,
108 human activities like forest clearing, mining, waste dumping and metallurgy have accelerated
109 the supply of heavy metals to coastal areas. Interpretation of the human influence, however,
110 requires knowledge of natural reference (background) concentrations, which can be obtained
111 from the pre-anthropogenic part of the estuarine sedimentary record.

112 Trace metals in the water column generally tend to be adsorbed onto fine, chemically
113 active particles in suspension, which are subsequently accreted to the sedimentary column.
114 Sedimentation of these metal-adsorbing particles incorporates the historical record of the
115 sources (both local and regional) of contaminant input into the host sediment (Hwang et al.,
116 2009). Where ¹⁴C-datable items are abundant, these sedimentary archives may therefore provide
117 time-resolved information for the reconstruction of historical changes in water quality, local
118 sedimentation and sea-level rise (Hartmann et al., 2005; Cantwell et al., 2007; Baker et al.,
119 2010). In estuaries affected by acid mine drainage (AMD), natural salt-induced
120 coagulation/precipitation processes, through which suspended elements in particulate matter are
121 incorporated onto sediments (Stecko and Bendell-Young, 2000), are altered. These
122 environments are characterized by high sulphate, metal and metalloid concentrations, the
123 behaviour of which is controlled by changes in pH and salinity. As a result, all these
124 behavioural modifications maybe reflected in the geochemical characteristics of the sediments
125 (Borrego et al., 2004).

126 Catchments of the Iberian Pyrite Belt in SW Iberia have been widely documented on
127 account of their massive sulphide deposits and associated intensive mining. The extraction of
128 minerals from these deposits dates back to the age of the Iberians and Tartessos, some 5000
129 years ago (Davis et al., 2000; Leblanc et al., 2000; Nocete et al., 2005). Acid discharges from
130 these mineral extractions into the river network almost inevitably left a chemical imprint in the
131 geological record. Hence, sedimentary geochemistry should be a powerful tool to trace
132 environmental changes in the area, induced both by natural and anthropogenic causes. Previous
133 investigations have indeed shown that study of sediments at depth may help establish the effects
134 of natural and anthropogenic processes in sedimentary environments (van Geen et al., 1997;
135 Leblanc et al., 2000; Borrego et al., 2004; Price et al., 2005; López-González et al., 2006;
136 Chatterjee et al., 2007; Viguri et al., 2007; Hwang et al., 2009).

137 Various studies have examined aspects of coastal sedimentation systems in the vicinity
138 of the Guadiana River, which crosses the final section (Fig. 1) of the Iberian Pyrite Belt. For
139 example, Morales (1993) and Morillo et al. (2004) provided geochemical data on sediments at
140 the coast near Huelva, González et al. (2007) characterized sediments on the Gulf of Cádiz
141 shelf, and Ruiz (2001) made an assessment of estuarine pollution levels. Gonzalez-Vila et al.
142 (2003) and Polvillo et al. (2009) presented data on organic geochemical markers to infer aspects
143 of the history of vegetation, diagenesis of organic matter and possible anthropogenic
144 interference, as well as on climatic and environmental changes (mainly derived from changes in
145 sea-level) during the Holocene-Anthropocene.

146 Historically, the waters in the Lower Basin of the Guadiana River have received acid
147 input from mining activity (Delgado et al., 2009), thus the surface sediments of the estuary
148 contain significant levels of contamination associated with this input (Delgado et al., 2010;

149 2011). However, there are no detailed data concerning the postglacial input of toxic metals to
150 the estuary. A thorough examination of historic variations in contaminant elements and the
151 establishment of the background metal concentrations are important precursors to an assessment
152 of anthropogenic impact on these environments (Mil-Homens et al., 2006). Such studies may
153 also provide valuable data on the behaviour of metals in estuarine settings that have been
154 historically affected by AMD.

155 Given the exceptionally long sedimentary record accumulated since the LGM in the
156 Guadiana River Estuary, the present study aims to bring together existing information on
157 sedimentary evolution in the area and to propose the first regional curve for postglacial sea-level
158 rise (SLR) in the Gulf of Cádiz, embracing the terminal Pleistocene and Holocene. From a
159 geochemical perspective, our goal is to establish background values for contaminant elements
160 and discriminate between natural and anthropogenic inputs of these elements into the system.
161 This information will complement an existing pollen-based reconstruction of environmental
162 change in the Lower Guadiana Basin, as proposed by Fletcher et al. (2003).

163

164 *1.1. Study area and historical perspective*

165

166 The Guadiana River is the fourth-longest river on the Iberian Peninsula, with a total
167 length of 810km. The last 200km stretch forms a natural border between Portugal and Spain. In
168 geological terms, the estuary is located almost entirely in the Central Domain (Iberian Pyrite
169 Belt) of the South-Portuguese Zone (Simancas et al., 2004). Its Late Quaternary geological
170 framework has been described in several previous works (Boski et al., 2002; Gonzalez-Vila et
171 al., 2003; Boski et al., 2008; Delgado et al., 2009). In a physical sense, the Guadiana Estuary
172 covers the zone of tidal influence extending 50km upstream of the point where the river
173 debouches into the Atlantic Ocean (Ruiz et al., 1996) (Fig. 1). The main estuarine channel
174 varies in depth between 2 and 14m and experiences a semi-diurnal mesotidal regime, with
175 maximum spring-tide amplitude reaching 3.44m (Garel et al., 2009). A schematic cross-section,
176 based on exploratory geotechnical drilling and seismic profiles, shows that the estuary's
177 palaeovalley was 600m wide and approximately 70m deep, 8km north from the mouth (Boski et
178 al., 2002). In contrast to the sedimentary infill characteristic of other estuaries in the region
179 (soft, unconsolidated sediments from the Plio-Pleistocene accumulated in large, shallow
180 structures valleys: Borrego et al., 1999), the Guadiana has thick (70-80m) Lateglacial and
181 Holocene deposits, enabling high-resolution temporal analysis of the sedimentary record (Boski
182 et al., 2002). For the purpose of this study, core materials from two deep boreholes were used:
183 CM5 and CM6, which define a NW-SE cross-section approximately 9km upstream from the
184 mouth (Fig. 1).

185 The Iberian Pyrite Belt (IPB), through which the Guadiana runs, is one of the most
186 important metallogenic provinces in the world, with original reserves of about 1700 million
187 tonnes of sulphides (Sáez et al., 1999). In line with archaeological evidence, the extraction of
188 minerals in the IPB started in the third millennium BC, and focused on the production of copper
189 (Davis et al., 2000; Leblanc et al., 2000; Nocete et al., 2005). During the first millennium BC,
190 silver was targeted. Silver and gold extraction developed on a larger scale during Roman times
191 (2000-1800 BP). Subsequent cultures, including the Visigoths and Arabs (1600-500 BP),
192 essentially abandoned mining operations (Davis et al., 2000). It was not until the first half of the
193 18th century that mining recommenced, this time by the United Kingdom, spurred initially by
194 demand for copper and, later, for sulphuric acid. These mines were large-scale, open-pit
195 operations (van Geen et al., 1997). The largest volumes of pyrite were extracted in the late 19th
196 century and early 20th century, until the activity finally ceased in the 1990s.

197 In the study area, the São Domingos Mine in Portugal and the Tharsis and Las Herrerías
198 Mines in Spain (Fig. 1) stand out for their area of production. Tharsis follows an exploitation
199 pattern very similar to that described above for the IPB in general. The São Domingos site has
200 been worked since the Chalcolithic, although intense exploitation began in Roman times
201 (Álvarez-Valero et al., 2008). Mineral extraction at São Domingos was especially intensive
202 from 1857 to 1966 (Matos et al., 2002), exposing the Guadiana Estuary to serious
203 contamination. The Las Herrerías Mine's production peaked in 1880, with the arrival of the
204 English company, The Bedel Metal and Chemical Co. Ltd., which was interested in pyrite
205 extraction instead of manganese. After successive changes in ownership that went on for about a
206 century, mining activity ceased in 1988. At the height of production, important minerals from
207 the main mines in the area (Las Herrerías, El Lagunazo, Cabezo del Pasto and Sardón) were
208 transported by rail to Puerto de la Laja (upstream of the study area) and exported by ship.

210 **2. Materials and methods**

212 *2.1. Borehole data*

214 We studied the sedimentological and geochemical characteristics of two deep sediment
215 cores: CM5 (51m deep, 6" in diameter) and CM6 (63m deep, 3" in diameter) (Fig. 1). Borehole
216 CM5 was positioned in an area of intertidal salt marshes close to the confluence of the Beliche
217 Rivulet and the Guadiana main channel. Borehole CM6 was positioned within the intertidal
218 zone of salt marshes covering the lateral sediment bank of the main channel on the Spanish side
219 of the river. The vertical elevation of the mouths of the two boreholes described in this work, as
220 well as that of 3 additional Guadiana boreholes (Boski et al., 2002; their location on the
221 Guadiana saltmarshes are shown in Fig. 2) used in the construction of the local sea-level curve,

222 were 2 - 5cm below the upper reaches of spring-tides. Considering that the maximum spring-
223 tide amplitude in the estuary is 3.4m, we assigned a vertical elevation of 1.7m above mean sea-
224 level (MSL) to all 5 boreholes. Overall core recovery was close to 90% for silt/clay sediments
225 and 70% for sand/gravel sediments. Only one 1.3m segment, probably of sand/sandy silt, was
226 lost entirely during the drilling of borehole CM6.

227 Prior to sample extraction, the cores were photographed and macroscopically described
228 in terms of lithology, presence of sedimentary structures and macrofossil content.

229

230 2.2. Sample collection and analytical procedures

231

232 Based on the chronostratigraphic model established from the CM5 profile (Boski et al.,
233 2008), sampling frequency in each core was defined as follows: (1) samples were collected
234 every 20cm in the top 6m to characterize the variations in metal content due to recent human
235 activity; (2) samples were taken every 50cm from 6–12m to characterize environmental changes
236 and other human activities in the drainage basin; (3) samples were collected every 2m below
237 12m to complete the geochemical characterization of estuarine infill and to establish the
238 background levels of elements. Sub-sampling for dating, grain-size analysis, and geochemical
239 analysis was performed in 1cm-thick subsamples. Wet sediments were placed rapidly into
240 porcelain containers and desiccated in a SELECTA DIGITHEAT 2001245 (150l) oven at a
241 temperature no higher than 40° C to remove moisture without causing mineralogical changes
242 within the samples. The samples were sieved through a 2mm mesh and divided into two sub-
243 samples, one for grain-size study and the other for chemical analysis.

244 The grain-size distribution of the fine fraction was analysed with a Malvern Mastersizer
245 2000[®] particle-size analyser, using sediment samples suspended in distilled water, to which 0.5g
246 of Sodium hexametaphosphate antiflocculant solution was added.

247 A total of 50 and 55 samples were selected from cores CM5 and CM6, respectively, to
248 characterize the geochemistry of the estuary's postglacial infill. The dried samples were ground
249 to 63 µm using a mechanical agate mortar. Total element concentrations were analyzed by
250 Acme Analytical Laboratories Ltd. (Vancouver, Canada), accredited under ISO 9002, through
251 its Italian affiliate (ERS srl, Napoli). Major elements and a number of trace elements indicative
252 of possible environmental impact (i.e. As, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, Pb, and Zn) were
253 determined by optical (ICP-AES) and mass (ICP-MS) spectrometry. Other parameters such as
254 total carbon (TC) and total sulphur (TS) were determined using a LECO elemental analyzer and
255 the sum of volatile substances was quantified by Loss on Ignition (LOI) at 1050° C.

256 The accuracy of measurements was calculated based on Acme's in-house reference
257 materials: DS7 and SO-18. Reference materials DS7 and SO-18 were calibrated to an *aqua*
258 *regia* digestion/ICP-MS determination against published values for a concentrated HCl and

259 HNO₃ digestion of the Canadian Certified Reference Materials Project (CCRMP) TILL-4 and
260 LKSD-2 (CANMET Mining and Mineral Sciences Laboratories Ottawa, ON, Canada).

261 In addition, to check the quality of the analysis, four replicates were analyzed. From
262 them, the Relative Percentage Difference (% RPD) was calculated as:

$$263 \quad \% RPD = (S-D)/(S+D)/2 \times 100 \quad (1)$$

264 Where: S=determined value of the samples, and D=value of the duplicates. The results for %
265 RPD (Table 1) are reasonably good and close to zero, the expected value. Most values are below
266 0.5%, except for Cr at 2.14%. No values are higher than 5% RPD.

267 Evaluation of the analytical performance of the total concentration was made by
268 analyzing the Certified Reference Materials (CRMs) STSD-1 and STSD-2 (the standard for
269 stream sediments). The measured concentrations of all 29 elements overlap, or are very close to,
270 the certified reference values for this standard (Table 1). Recovery ranges were calculated by:

$$271 \quad \% Recovery = (Obtained\ value/Certified\ value) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

272 Generally, the ranges of recovery of the principal elements under study (Fe, Al, As, Cd, Co, Cr,
273 Cu, Ni, Pb, and Zn) are between 78.5 and 105 %, except Cd and Cr, which do not have certified
274 reference values. There is a good level of agreement between our results and the reference
275 values (Table 1).

276

277 2.3. ¹⁴C time-scale and micropalaeontological analysis

278

279 For the purpose of establishing the age models for both postglacial sedimentary profiles,
280 the ¹⁴C ages of datable items preserved in the sediment were determined according to Table 2.
281 Dated items, in order of preference for dating, were: autochthonous organic matter, wood
282 fragments, entire bivalve shells and dispersed organic matter. Organic matter samples were
283 freeze-dried after sectioning the cores, in order to avoid introduction of “young carbon” from
284 bacteria and fungi that may colonize the sediment particles (Wohlfarth et al., 1998). Dispersed
285 sedimentary organic matter was graphitized and submitted to AMS measurement after removal
286 of carbonates and humic and fulvic acids. Radiocarbon ages were calibrated using the program
287 CALIB v. 6.0 (Stuiver and Reimer, 2009; Reimer et al., 2009). A marine reservoir correction of
288 328 years, available from the CALIB database, was applied to marine carbonate samples. All
289 radiocarbon dates are expressed in calibrated calendar years (cal. BP) as the midpoints of
290 2σ confidence intervals (Table 2).

291 The foraminiferal assemblages of borehole CM5 have been described in previous
292 investigations (Fletcher et al., 2007; Boski et al., 2008). From the new borehole, CM6, a total of
293 75 samples were examined for their benthic foraminiferal content. Samples were sieved through
294 500µm and 63µm meshes after decanting away organic debris. After sieving, samples with a
295 high sand content were dried and the sediment sprinkled with carbon tetrachloride to float off

296 the foraminifera. Samples with large total numbers of foraminifera were divided with a
297 modified plankton splitter (Scott and Hermelin, 1993), which divided the sample into eight
298 equal parts in order to reduce the total number of individuals to statistically representative count
299 of 300-400. In samples with few identifiable foraminifera, however, 100 individuals were
300 considered to be sufficient (Fatela and Taborda, 2002). Processed samples were examined under
301 a binocular microscope in a gridded, circular counting tray. Species diversity was assessed with
302 Shannon diversity index (H').

303 In several samples, diatoms were also identified and counted to better define marine
304 influence in the sedimentary record. Approximately 1g of sediment was cleaned in H_2O_2 and
305 HCl to eliminate organic matter and carbonates. Microscope slides were prepared with a
306 measured volume of solution containing diatoms and mounted in Naphrax for identification and
307 counting (Round et al., 1990). Approximately 150 to 300 diatom valves per sample were
308 identified and counted.

309

310 *2.4. Statistical analyses*

311

312 Factor analysis (FA) was applied to determine the sources of metals from the two
313 sedimentary cores. This technique has been widely used to distinguish natural and
314 anthropogenic elemental contributions to sediments and to determine the factors that control
315 their geochemical behaviour in the estuarine system, based on the variable levels of association
316 (Ayyamperumal et al., 2006; Covelli et al., 2006; Wu et al., 2007; Katahira et al., 2009). The
317 values of the factor matrix can be improved by using the varimax rotation method, which
318 maximizes factor variance (Kaiser et al., 1958). An orthogonal rotation minimises the number
319 of variables that have high loadings on each factor, simplifying the transformed data matrix and
320 assisting interpretation.

321 The FA output was presented in terms of: (a) factor loadings, which display the
322 correlations that exist between the original variables (Jolliffe, 2002), and (b) factor scores,
323 which represent the distribution of the principal components in space (in this case, depth).

324 Statistical analysis of the data was performed using the STATISTICA 7.0 software
325 package (StatSoft, USA).

326

327 **3. Results and discussion**

328

329 *3.1. Sedimentary facies*

330

331 The classification of sedimentary facies in both borehole profiles was based on their
332 textural features and foraminiferal content, complemented by diatom counts in samples where
333 dissolution of foraminifera tests could occur. Given the site specificity of time-space evolution
334 in a estuarine environments, a Foraminiferal Indicator of Marine Influence (FIMI) was applied
335 for the purpose of classification. The FIMI (Boski et al., 2008) may ranges from 1, in fluvial
336 environments with no foraminifera, to 5, in open estuarine environments in which the
337 foraminiferal assemblage is entirely calcareous, containing numerous shelf species and also
338 planktonic species. Intermediate values are defined according to the proportions between
339 agglutinated and calcareous species.

340

341 *3.1.1. Lithology and foraminifera fauna: boreholes CM5 and CM6*

342

343 The lithological profiles of the two boreholes and graphs depicting FIMI values and the
344 changing composition of foraminiferal assemblages in borehole CM6 are shown in Fig. 3. The
345 detailed description of foraminiferal assemblages in borehole CM5 was presented by Boski et
346 al. (2008). Both sedimentary sequences have accumulated on top of a coarse to very coarse
347 basal gravel layer (Unit I), which was deposited by the Guadiana River during a past marine
348 lowstand. Unit I sits directly on top of the Carboniferous shale/greywacke substratum at depths
349 of 50.8m in CM5 and 72.5m in CM6. Similar basal gravel layers have been described in other
350 estuaries around the Gulf of Cádiz (Borrego et al., 1999).

351

352 *3.1.1.1. Description of the sedimentary profile in borehole CM5 (Beliche Rivulet)*

353

354 *Unit II (depth 48.6 – 40.8m). Transition from fluvial to estuarine saltmarsh facies.*

355 FIMI 1 to 2. The silt and fine micaceous sand intercalations in the first three metres of this unit
356 indicate a transition from fluviially- to tidally-conditioned sedimentation. The first foraminiferal
357 fauna (agglutinated *Trochammina*, typical for upper saltmarsh) and indicating a marine
358 influence were detected at a depth of 44.9m. The complex Fe–Ca–Mg and Mn carbonate
359 structures described in this unit (Boski et al., 2008) are scavenging sites where several heavy
360 metal elements are concentrated (see geochemical section). The sediment characteristics
361 indicate that marine transgression started between the dated point at 47.67 (wood, Table 2) and
362 the next dated level at 42.7m, with radiocarbon ages of 12835yr cal. BP and 12015yr cal. BP,
363 respectively.

364

365 *Unit III (depth 40.8 – 24.5m). Estuarine saltmarsh facies.*

366 FIMI 2. This unit is composed of dark grey silt with sporadic centimetric laminae distinguished
367 by a high content of macerated plant remains. In terms of the foraminiferal fauna, the diversity

368 of which is low, the entire sequence is dominated by inner linings and agglutinated
369 *Trochamminas* pp.

370

371 Unit IV (depth 24.5 – 4.2m). *Open estuarine, mudflat facies.*

372 FIMI 3 – 4. This silty unit contains a highly diverse foraminiferal assemblage, indicating the
373 greatest marine influence in the entire profile. The co-dominance of *Ammonia beccarii* and
374 *Haynesina germanica*, associated with *Elphidium* spp. and exotic (shelf) *Brizalina* spp., reflects
375 an estuarine environment open to the free circulation of shelf waters.

376

377 Unit V (4.2 – 0m). *Confined, estuarine saltmarsh facies.*

378 FIMI 2. The foraminiferal assemblages of this uppermost segment of the borehole are
379 dominated by an association of *Trochammina macrescens* and *Trochammina inflata*. Its top 2m
380 displays prominent mottling, probably due to exposure to oxidizing conditions. This unit marks
381 a final stage in the infilling of the estuary.

382

383 *3.1.1.2. Description of the sedimentary profile in borehole CM6*

384

385 Unit I (depth 72.2 – 63.4m). *Fluvial gravel unit.*

386 Only the first 30 centimetres of Unit I, composed of coarse fluvial gravels, could be recovered
387 by the mechanical drilling rig. However, by inserting a steel rod into the gravel, it was possible
388 to establish the bottom limit of this fluvial horizon at a depth of 72.2m, i.e. at the contact with
389 the Carboniferous shale/greywacke substratum.

390

391 Unit II (depth 63.4 – 62.5m). *Open estuarine mudflat facies.*

392 FIMI 5. A dark grey silty unit containing abundant benthic foraminiferal fauna, almost entirely
393 calcareous, with *Asterigerinata mamilla* dominant and associated with the estuarine species
394 *Ammonia beccarii* and *Haynesina germanica* (<10% of the total). Planktonic species account
395 for about 10% of the assemblage and indicate free water exchange with the marine environment.
396 No ¹⁴C-datable items were recovered in this horizon. However, the foraminiferal assemblage
397 has the most marine character in the entire borehole profile and points to a sea-level comparable
398 to, or even higher than, the Holocene highstand. The unit may be tentatively interpreted as a
399 remnant of the sedimentary record corresponding to the transgression preceding the MIS 5e
400 marine highstand.

401

402 Unit III (depth 62.5 – 57.5m). *Fluvial facies.*

403 FIMI 1. This horizon is also composed of silts, but of generally lighter colour than the
404 underlying estuarine sequence. Foraminifera are totally absent in this sediment. There are

405 frequent couplets of dark-grey silts and lighter-coloured micaceous sandy silts, most probably
406 resulting from deposition on a floodplain adjacent to the main river channel.

407

408 Unit IV (depth 57.5m – 51.8). Estuarine saltmarsh facies.

409 FIMI 2. This unit is composed of dark, fine silts and marine influence is firmly established
410 through a fauna of agglutinated saltmarsh species *Trochammina macrescens* and the internal
411 linings of the calcareous species, *Ammonia beccarii* and *Haynesina germanica*. Diatoms are
412 very abundant in 5 of the 6 samples taken from the unit, with dominant species (*Nitzschia*
413 *navicularis*, *Scolioneis tumida* and *Diploneis didyma*) typical of brackish to littoral ecosystems.
414 The poor preservation of foraminifera tests and diatom frustules (particularly in the sample from
415 53.0m), is certainly due to the acidification of sediment containing disseminated acid volatile
416 sulphides (AVS). Indeed a routine pH check of the sampled sediment at a depth of 53m gave a
417 pH of 3. Two geochronological reference points were obtained in this section. At the depth of
418 55.0m, dispersed sediment organic matter gave an age of 13241yr cal. BP and at 52.45m-depth
419 a 3cm-thick wood fragment, filling the entire core section, yielded an age of 12961yr cal. BP.

420

421 Unit V (depth 51.8 – 48.8m). Fluvial - upper saltmarsh facies.

422 FIMI 1 -2. The mostly silty sediments of Unit V, with their light yellowish laminae attesting to
423 periods of subaerial exposure, are totally void of foraminifera. Only a few, poorly preserved
424 frustules of *Nitzschia navicularis* were observed. The uppermost 1.2m, probably silty sand, was
425 not recovered in the core barrel. The unit's features point once more to a transitional
426 fluvial/upper estuarine floodplain facies established during a period of sea-level stabilization or
427 slight retreat. Taking into consideration the ¹⁴C ages obtained in the underlying unit IV, this
428 interval could well correspond to the Younger Dryas, as Fletcher et al. (2007) proposed for the
429 lowermost segment of the CM5 profile.

430

431 Unit VI (depth 48.8 – 24.5m). Estuarine saltmarsh facies.

432 FIMI 2. This unit is composed of homogenous grey silts, with mean particle size ranging from
433 13 to 35 µm and containing occasional mudclasts produced by bioturbation. In the 34 samples
434 analyzed, the foraminiferal assemblage is dominated by agglutinated species *Trochammina*
435 *macrescens* and calcareous estuarine species, *Ammonia beccarii* and *Haynesina germanica*,
436 often preserved as inner linings. Several samples (i.e., 41.5, 40.3, 33.3, 28.7m) contain no
437 foraminifera at all. The lack of tests is attributed to their dissolution, because the samples thus
438 affected occur in between intervals where foraminifera were abundant.

439

440 Unit VII (depth 24.5 – 13.5m). Estuarine mudflat facies.

441 FIMI 4. Sediment in this interval is slightly coarser than in the underlying unit, with mean grain
442 size ranging from 17 to 66 μm . It is composed of dark, sandy silts and contains abundant
443 bivalve fragments. The upper limit of the unit is erosional and marks a transition to a high-
444 energy channel environment. *Ammonia beccarii* and *Haynesina germanica* dominate the
445 foraminiferal assemblage. *Elphidium advenum* and other calcareous species were also frequent.
446 From the bottom to the top of the horizon, Shannon diversity index (H') rises from 1 to 2.2,
447 pointing to more frequent tidal inundation than in the previous unit. Foraminifera were absent in
448 several sections, probably due to post-depositional dissolution. Preliminary observation of these
449 sections, centred on 23.8 and 22.9m, revealed the presence of estuarine/coastal diatoms, namely
450 *Nitzschia navicularis*, *Fragilaria brevistriata*, *Gomphonema parvulum* and *Ephitemia adnata*.
451 Two radiocarbon ages, obtained from dispersed organic matter at 19.0m and on a *Cerastoderma*
452 sp. shell at 14.03m, gave ages of 8235 and 6902yr cal. BP, respectively. These figures provide a
453 time constraint on the terminal period of rapid sea-level rise in the CM6 sedimentary record.

454

455 *Unit VIII (depth 13.1 – 0m). Channel facies evolving to mudflat and saltmarsh facies.*

456 FIMI 1-5. From the bottom gravels and coarse sands containing shell debris, this unit becomes
457 progressively more fine-grained towards the surface, where the silty sediment indicates a
458 transition from a channel situation to a lower energy environment of mudflats and saltmarshes.
459 As a whole, the unit formed during the build-up of an estuarine meander bar, evolving from a
460 deeper, more energetic environment to a shallower, intertidal depositional environment. The
461 emplacement of the meander occurred most probably under the influence of the “Arroyo
462 Pedroza”, an ephemeral, now extinct creek, which once drained a small tributary valley joining
463 the principal estuarine channel near the borehole site.

464 The foraminiferal assemblage, which was well preserved in 4 of the 5 silt samples analysed, is
465 dominated by *Ammonia beccarii* and *Haynesina germanica*, accompanied by *Elphidium*
466 *advenum*, *Elphidium excavatum*, *Cibicides lobatulus* and *Haynesina depressula*. In the 3
467 uppermost metres of the core where foraminifera were absent, diatoms were abundant, with the
468 leading species *Nitzschia navicularis*, *Pinnularia borealis*, *Fragilaria brevistriata* and *Navicula*
469 cf. *laevissima*.

470

471 *3.1.2. Sea-level change and sediment infilling of the Guadiana Estuary through the terminal*
472 *Pleistocene and Holocene*

473

474 The curve of sea-level rise proposed in this work is based on 28 radiocarbon dates from
475 the 5 sediment cores: CM5 and CM6 (Boski et al., 2008; present study) and CM1, CM2 and
476 CM3 (Boski et al., 2002). Most of the dated items were identified bivalve shells (19) and the
477 remainders were peat/peaty sediment, wood fragments and dispersed organic matter. There are

478 several sources of uncertainty in determining the past sea-level elevation with respect to the
479 present MSL through the dating of organic or carbonate items retrieved from the sediment
480 cores. With no evidence of recent tectonic movements along the S. Portuguese continental
481 margin, the four main sources of error, and the respective error margins may be estimated as
482 follows: i) elevation of the borehole mouth with respect to the present MSL: $\pm 20\text{cm}$ (see section
483 2.1), ii) depth below the borehole mouth from which the dated item was recovered: $\pm 20\text{cm}$, (due
484 to the incomplete core recovery), iii) position of dated items recovered from the
485 mudflat/saltmarsh units with respect to the past MSL: $\pm 1.4\text{m}$ (equal to the present mean tidal
486 range amplitude), and iv) position of dated items recovered from channel facies with respect to
487 the past MSL: -5m (equal to the average depth of the main tidal channel in the area of
488 boreholes).

489 Sediment compaction was not taken into account because peat, usually the most
490 compaction-prone material in sediment profiles, was all but absent in the studied cores, apart
491 from some layers of a few centimetres in thickness. According to our previous studies, sediment
492 density, and consequently the volume of sediments, does not change significantly below the first
493 20cm of sedimentary column (Boski et al., 2008).

494 A linear age/depth relation for the process of palaeovalley infilling since the LGM was
495 established for borehole CM5 by Boski et al. (2008) and has been completed for borehole CM6
496 in this work (Fig. 4). According to our interpretation, both sequences seem to have mostly
497 accumulated in an intertidal environment either an unvegetated mudflat or saltmarsh. The rate of
498 infilling is represented by linear regression of the depth/age relation (Fig. 4), which is split into
499 two separate phases. The earlier phase corresponds to a period of rapid sea-level rise (13000–
500 7200yr cal. BP), with a sediment accumulation rate of ca. 7.3mm/yr from the CM5 borehole and
501 6.6mm/yr from the 3 newly dated samples from the CM6 borehole. In the subsequent phase,
502 from 7200yr cal. BP onwards, the sediment accumulation rate decelerated to ca. 1.2mm/yr and
503 2.4mm/yr from CM5 and CM6, respectively. This difference in accretion rates arises from
504 differences in sedimentary dynamics and accommodation space at the two sites. While CM5's
505 accretion occurred continuously in the sheltered intertidal zone, the upper portion of the CM6
506 profile corresponded initially to deeper channel facies, progressively evolving into intertidal
507 mudflat and saltmarsh facies.

508 As noted above, the first foraminifera-rich estuarine unit, at the bottom of borehole
509 CM6, did not yield any datable items and was tentatively attributed to the last interglacial,
510 possibly the MIS 5e highstand. The first chronological evidence of marine influence in the
511 Guadiana Estuary came from dating disseminated organic matter and a wood fragment. Both
512 ages, 13241yr cal. BP and 12961yr cal. BP, precede the first cooling phase of the Younger
513 Dryas stadial at ca. 12.6kyr, which may have led to a slight drop in sea-level (Rodrigues et al.,
514 2010). On the NW Spanish continental margin, in the area of "Ría de Vigo", YD regression has

515 been inferred from a seismic/erosional discontinuity at 45m depth below the present sea-level
516 (García-García et al., 2005). It seems that this brief regression did not produce any observable
517 erosion in either of the Guadiana records, but was sufficient to impede development of brackish
518 foraminiferal fauna during the deposition of unit V, classified as fluvial facies. At the location
519 of CM5, near the confluence of the Beliche Rivulet and the Guadiana River, the palaeovalley
520 was still too shallow to allow the accumulation of estuarine sediments at that time.
521 Consequently, vegetal remains dated 12835yr cal. BP in borehole CM5 belong to the fluvial
522 phase of sedimentation, contemporaneous with a climatic phase that was cooler and drier than
523 the subsequent phase in the lower Guadiana Basin (Fletcher et al., 2007). Brackish conditions
524 were detected in CM5 close to the second dated point, i.e. 12015yr cal. BP. This age is slightly
525 earlier than the beginning of the Holocene transgression, which, according to Smith et al.
526 (2011), begun at 11650yr cal. BP. The curve of sea-level rise presented in Figure 5 is a 2-
527 segment regression line based on 28 index points. The 5 index points from channel facies have
528 been corrected by adding the average value of channel depth, i.e. 5m. The lower segment of the
529 regression line (Fig. 5) points to sea-level rise occurring at a rate $6.8\text{mm}\cdot\text{yr}^{-1}$ until ca. 7500yr
530 cal. BP. Correlation for that time laps ($R^2 = 0.946$) points to a spatially coherent trend, with the
531 possible exception of the CM3 borehole, whose sedimentary record accumulated to large extent
532 in channel facies. The dated fragment of abraded wood from a depth of 26.9m is clearly an
533 outlier, being excessively old, probably much older than the age of active sediment surface on
534 which it was deposited and was therefore not considered in the computation of the regression
535 line. Scrutiny of the position of sea-level index points dated between 8500 and 7500yr cal. BP
536 (Fig. 5) indicates that the sea-level could have risen at an even faster rate than the figure
537 proposed above. Indeed, this period corresponds to the last melt water pulse from the collapsing
538 Laurentide ice sheet (Clarke et al., 2004, Turney et al., 2007, Hijma and Cohen, 2010). Van der
539 Schriek et al. (2007) reported a widespread intrusion of saltwater into the Lower Tagus Valley
540 in Central Portugal during that period. However, the fact that the error in depth estimation is
541 quite large in the 5 of the 10 age-points corresponding to channel facies calls for some caution
542 in interpretation. The period from the mid Holocene to the present witnessed a much slower, ca.
543 $1.8\text{mm}\cdot\text{yr}^{-1}$, sea-level rise, whose record is less coherent because of the more limited
544 accommodation space for the sediments and the more complex sedimentary dynamics imposed
545 by the closer proximity of the shore-line. Deposition of both terrigenous and shelf sediments
546 was less continuous and possibly interrupted by erosional events, i.e. when sediment supply
547 surpasses accommodation (Stanley and Warne, 1994). The less linear accretion trend for the
548 latter part of the Holocene may relate to the fact that most of the dated items from that period
549 were bivalve shells, which were not necessarily sampled in their original living position.

550 Overall, the presented curve (which could be more accurately described as a band)
551 complements the SLR curve proposed by Dias et al. (2000) for the N part of the Portuguese

552 shelf on the basis of bathymetric, geomorphological and relative ages, however with very
553 limited chronological data. Vis et al. (2008) proposed a SLR curve for the Tagus Valley
554 matching very closely the one proposed in this study in the period postdating 8890yr cal. BP.
555 Below that date, the match is not satisfactory because the Tagus curve is based on only 2 index
556 points, whose intertidal position is deduced solely from the presence of pyrite. In a wider, global
557 context, the sedimentary record of SLR in the Guadiana Valley bears strong similarities to the
558 Yangtze Estuary, where Liu et al. (2010) have documented the postglacial transgression for the
559 last 12kyr. However, their proposed sea-level for 12kyr, ranging from ~53-62m below present
560 MSL, is some 15m below our projection. The Guadiana curve seems to accord with the coral-
561 derived records from Barbados (Peltier and Fairbanks, 2006) and Tahiti (Bard et al., 2010) until
562 ca. 11000yr cal. BP. For the earlier part of the two records, 11-13ka, the regression line in the
563 centre of our error envelope is 10-12m above the U – Th dated index points from Barbados with
564 a trend to increase in depth. The observed difference between the trend of global ice-equivalent
565 eustatic sea level curve and our line can be attributed to the age overestimation of Guadiana
566 index points, because there is no evidence of recent tectonic movements in the lower Guadiana
567 basin. In the cases of wood fragment and disseminated organic matter dating, such
568 overestimation may be in the order of hundreds of years.

569

570 *3.2. Geochemical characteristics*

571

572 Summary data for elements analyzed in the two sediment cores, including their granulometric
573 characteristics, are reported in Table 3.

574

575 *3.2.1. Major and trace elements*

576

577 Due to their siliciclastic nature, the sediments are composed mainly of SiO₂ and Al₂O₃, with
578 mean values of 57.5% and 16%, respectively. These are followed by Fe₂O₃ (5.96%), and Na₂O
579 and K₂O (≈ 2% each). The rest of the elements analyzed are present at mean concentrations
580 below 2%, with MnO reaching values of 0.06% (Table 3). The mean values for SiO₂ suggest a
581 moderate textural maturity of the sediments, evidenced by a SiO₂/Al₂O₃ ratio lower than 5. This
582 is due to the relative enrichment of Al-rich phyllosilicates at the expense of Si-rich phases,
583 which are produced in fine-grained sediments (Weltje and von Eynatten, 2004). Thus, a
584 decrease in the SiO₂/Al₂O₃ ratio is related to a decrease in grain size and, as a result, to a
585 decrease in textural maturity.

586 Fe₂O₃, MnO, K₂O, and P₂O₅ in the CM5 core and Fe₂O₃, MgO, K₂O, TiO₂, and P₂O₅ in
587 the CM6 core show moderately strong correlations with Al₂O₃ (Table 3), suggesting that most
588 of the major elements are associated with the clay aluminium-mineral group. The lack of a good

589 correlation between MnO and Al₂O₃ in CM6 is an important characteristic in interpreting the
590 geochemistry of sediments and is discussed further below.

591 The highest concentrations of trace elements are of Ba, Zr, Sr, and Rb, whose mean
592 values exceed 100ppm. These high values are associated with shell fragments in the case of Sr
593 and Rb, or with heavy minerals such as zircon in the case of Zr, which is very abundant in
594 nearby coastal sediments (Fernández-Caliani et al., 1997).

595 There are moderately elevated concentrations of elements that are potential
596 contaminants, mainly those associated with mining operations in the IPB. Zn shows a wide
597 range of values between 29 and 87ppm, with a mean of 67.7ppm (Table 3). The results for Ni
598 also stand out, with a range of 11.7–60.7ppm, and a mean value of 30ppm. Cu ranges from 9.7–
599 54ppm (mean 26ppm). Other elements include Pb, Co, As, and Cr with maximum (and mean)
600 values of 41.3 (18.7), 39.4 (15.8), 36.9 (14.6) and 27.2 (20.6) ppm, respectively. Cd
601 concentrations are also significant, up to 0.6ppm (a significant value, given the high toxicity of
602 this element), with a mean value of 0.09ppm. Chromium, Ni, Pb, and Zn have moderate,
603 positive correlations ($r > 0.44$) with Al₂O₃ in the CM5 core. Similar correlations with Al₂O₃ ($r >$
604 0.41) were also found for As, Co, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb, and Zn in CM6. On this basis, the variability
605 of these metals appears to be closely related to the percentage of clay present in the samples,
606 and hence with the clay aluminium-mineral group.

607

608 *3.2.2. Relationships between variables: Factor Analysis*

609

610 The three components determined by factor analysis explain 61.3% and 78.5% of the
611 total variance in the samples from cores CM5 and CM6, respectively. Figure 6 shows the factor
612 loadings derived from applying varimax rotation, and the variability of these factors according
613 to depth using factor scores. The statistical analysis provides important data for understanding
614 the relationships between sedimentological and geochemical processes during estuarine
615 infilling.

616 Factors I, II, and III explain 33.2, 14.9, and 13.2% and 54.5, 15.3, 8.7% of the total
617 variance for cores CM5 and CM6, respectively. Factor I is characterised by high positive
618 loadings (> 0.5) for clay %, Al, Fe, K, P, Mn, Cr, Cu, Sc, Ba, Rb, V, and U, and moderate
619 loadings (< 0.5) for Ni, Pb, and Zn in core CM5. Similarly, in CM6, Factor I shows high
620 loadings for clay %, Al, Fe, K, P, Mn, Mg, As, Co, Cr, Cu, Ni, Zn, Sc, Ba, Rb, V, and U, and a
621 moderate loading for Pb. Factor I negative loadings include Si-sand %, Na, Ca, Sr, TC, and TS
622 for both cores, apart from Cd and Hg for CM5. Factor II shows high positive loadings (> 0.5)
623 for Mg, Ca, Na, LOI, TC, TS, Sr, As, and a moderate loading for Fe in core CM5, and high
624 loadings for Mg, Na, LOI, TC, TS, Cd, and Cu for core CM6. Factor II also presents negative
625 loadings for Si and sand %. Factor III shows high positive loadings among Mn–Ti, Cd, Co, Ni,

626 Pb and, to a lesser degree, Cu and Zn in core CM5 and Mn–Mg, Ti, Co, Pb relationships in core
627 CM6.

628 In order to explain the variation of these factors with depth, factor scores were plotted in
629 Figure 6. The Factor I profile presents a strong similarity with clay content variations (see Fig.
630 3), namely, a sharp increase for both parameters at 15m depth and decrease above 7m depth in
631 core CM6. This similarity, along with the associations described above, indicates that Factor I
632 mainly represents geochemical inputs from soil and bedrock erosion (Wu et al., 2007) in the
633 basin. The relationship also indicates the known affinity of the metallic elements to the Al-clay
634 mineral group (López-González et al., 2006), which, in addition to the fundamental role played
635 by Fe-Mn oxyhydroxides, are responsible for the scavenging and subsequent deposition of these
636 elements by suspended matter in the estuary.

637 According to Borrego et al. (2004) the distribution of Factor II shows a clear association
638 with components of biogenic origin, such as LOI, TC, Ca, and Sr, in addition to carbonate
639 minerals (Ca, Mg, Na, and Fe), which can incorporate metal elements such as As, Cd, and Cu.
640 These carbonate minerals, such as *siderite* observed in core CM5, could form through
641 diagenetic oxidation of pyrite due to the high permeability of Unit III, which favours
642 groundwater circulation (Boski et al., 2008). This factor shows the mineral association
643 identified by Boski et al. (2008), confirming that this process should occur during diagenesis.
644 This would also account for the presence of TS in Factor II. TS explains the important role of
645 CaCO₃ in the absorption of trace metals that leach under acidic conditions (Ayyamperumal et
646 al., 2006) and which, therefore, have an origin clearly associated either with acid rock drainage
647 (ARD) and/or with postdepositional oxidation of sulphides under acidic conditions. The higher
648 factor scores of Factor II at ca.35m depth (core CM5) coincide with an increase in Sr
649 concentration. The increment of factor scores upwards of 20m-depth in both cores may be
650 related to bioclastic content, since the first macrofaunal remains appear from 24.5m.

651 Finally, the distribution of Factor III shows an important association between Mn and
652 metal elements such as Cd, Co, Ni, Pb, and Zn, and to a lesser extent, Cu, in core CM5, and Co
653 and Pb in core CM6, as previously described by Wu et al. (2007). These associations are
654 especially strong in the upper part of the cores (Fig. 6), which is indicative of the significant role
655 of Mn in the withdrawal of metals from the water during the last 4500 years (\approx 6.5m depth). As
656 a result, Factor III reflects elements strongly associated with human activity in recent times.

657

658 3.2.3. Geochemical markers and palaeo-environmental interpretations

659

660 To properly compare the concentration of an element between samples, it is necessary
661 to compensate for the effects of grain size by applying an appropriate correction (Aloupi and
662 Angelidis, 2001). Otherwise, for the same input conditions, fine-grained samples would exhibit

663 relatively high metal concentrations compared with samples having a higher sand content.
664 Although grain-size effects can be compensated by establishing a relationship between metal
665 concentrations and the grain-size distribution of each sample, it must be remembered that
666 particle size is not the sole factor controlling elemental concentrations. Thus, many authors
667 choose to normalise metal concentration using another element/component predominantly
668 associated with the clay size-fraction (Lee and Cundy, 2001). Among the components that have
669 been proposed as a base for normalisation are Al (Bertine and Goldberg, 1977; Carral et al.,
670 1995; Covelli et al., 2006), Li (Loring, 1991), Cs (Ackermann, 1980; Grousset et al., 1995), Fe
671 (Piper, 1971; Blomqvist et al., 1992; Herut et al., 1993; Cobelo-García and Prego, 2003), and
672 others, including Sc, grain size, and organic carbon. Fe and Al have been used most frequently
673 as normalising elements, both in marine and estuarine sediments (Cundy and Croudace, 1996).
674 This is because they are the principal constituents of the fine-grained aluminosilicates with
675 which metals are frequently associated (Windom et al., 1989; Loring and Rantala, 1992;
676 Daskalakis and O'Connor, 1995).

677 Simple linear regressions with 95% confidence intervals were calculated for Al, Fe, Cs,
678 Sc, and metals on Al_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 ; R^2 (correlation) values obtained when normalised with Al
679 were always higher (Fig. 7). Examples of these strong correlations with Al include Fe (0.89), Co
680 (0.60), Cr (0.92), Cu (0.66), Ni (0.92) and Zn (0.94). For this reason, we decided to use Al for
681 normalisation (Aloupi and Angelidis, 2001). Previous investigations in the study area (Delgado
682 et al., 2010) have shown that Al and heavy metals are associated with the clay fraction of the
683 surface sediments of the estuary. Aluminium and heavy metals are also strongly associated in
684 surficial waters of the drainage basin (Delgado et al., 2009). Moderate correlations between Al
685 and As (0.55) were found, whereas the weakest were for Pb (0.41) and Cd (0.22).

686 The M/Al ratio (metal normalised with respect to Al) may be a useful indicator of
687 natural or anthropogenic changes in the postglacial record. Temporal variations in the
688 concentrations of elements preferentially associated with the oxidation of massive sulphide
689 deposits (e.g. Fe, As, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb, and Zn) are shown in Fig. 8. Significant variations
690 in the M/Al ratio for the various metal elements evidently reflect changes in the depositional
691 environment of the sediments.

692 *Units II and IV* in core CM5 and CM6, respectively, correspond to the initial stage of
693 the post-glacial estuarine sedimentary record of the Iberian Peninsula. *Unit I* in both cores is the
694 legacy of a former fluvial regime that operated during past lowstands (equivalent units in the
695 estuaries of the Gulf of Cádiz have been described by Dabrio et al., 2000). Regularly
696 interbedded compact silts in *Unit II* (CM5) and *III* (CM6) point to the initial stages of an
697 intertidal environment. The change in sedimentation conditions is less evident in core CM6,
698 although the final units (*II* to *V*) do have similar sedimentary characteristics to those described
699 for the marine-fluvial transition. The transition from marine-fluvial mixed sedimentation to

700 purely fluvial sedimentation is recorded geochemically by significant variation in the
701 concentration of elements such as Fe, As, Cd, Co, and Pb, which tend to decrease drastically, as
702 do elements that are bioclastic in nature, such as Sr and Y. In contrast, Cr, Cu, Ni, and Zn tend
703 to increase (Fig. 8), and are associated with other elements that are clearly lithophile in nature,
704 such as Ba and Ti, and M/Al maximum values.

705 Most of the analysed elements do not vary significantly in terms of their concentrations
706 in the central sections of both profiles (12–41m in CM5 and 13–47.5m in CM6, corresponding
707 to *Units IV–V* and *Units VI–VII* respectively), with the exception of As, which varies
708 significantly through the entire record. The benthic foraminifera assemblage, which is
709 associated with an abundance of bivalve shells and large quantity of halophyte pollen (Fletcher
710 et al., 2007), indicate clearly that *Unit IV* from CM5 was deposited in an intertidal zone that
711 evolved from a mudflat to a saltmarsh environment (*Unit V*). The increase in faunal content with
712 depth correlates well with variations in the Sr/Al ratio (not plotted), increasing dramatically
713 from 6 (at 20m depth) to 9 at the surface. Likewise, Sr presents a significant peak, coinciding
714 with the only noticeable variation of Fe in the entire core CM5. The co-variation of these
715 elements, associated in Factor II (see section 3.2.2 above), could be the result of post-
716 depositional sulphide oxidation (Fe, As, and Cu), creating low-pH conditions and corrosion of
717 carbonate items (Ca, Sr, and TC). Both phenomena were documented by Boski et al. (2008) in
718 core CM5. *Unit VI* of core CM6, with a geochemical behaviour similar to that described for core
719 CM5, has also lithological characteristics that define a typical low-energy, estuarine
720 sedimentary environment. On top of *Unit VII* (from 24.5m, in CM6 core) another increase in the
721 Sr/Al ratio is apparent, and coincides with the maximum abundance of shell fragments (see Fig.
722 3) and substantially coarser grain size of sediment accumulated in a point bar.

723 Finally, upwards of 12m depth in both cores (i.e. since ca. 7800 cal. BP), substantial
724 variations in elemental concentrations are observed. Broadly speaking, all elements associated
725 with the exploitation of massive sulphides tend to increase until post-Roman times (ca. 1800
726 cal. BP). Since previous studies of biogeochemical markers found only very tenuous
727 associations with sea-level fluctuations in the Guadiana sedimentary record (Gonzalez-Vila et
728 al., 2003), it is likely that the modulation of elemental fluxes is associated with anthropogenic
729 activity in the Guadiana basin, such as tree felling, farming and, primarily, mining activity in the
730 IPB. In this context, the coarsening sediment grain size and abundant fragments of bivalve
731 shells in the base of *Unit VII* (CM6 core) suggest that this unit was deposited under increasing
732 energy conditions during the Neolithic period. In the uppermost *Unit VIII*, two horizons of
733 medium to coarse sands were laid down in a growing meander bar, fed by the sediments from
734 tributary creek “Arroyo Pedroza”. Increasing sediment delivery to the S Portuguese coastal zone
735 was also observed by Chester and James (1991) and Allen (2003), who proposed that the
736 decrease in the intertidal area of local estuaries occurred during an “alluviation” stage of the late

737 Holocene. They attribute this process to the above mentioned anthropogenic causes, which are
738 widely documented and support the idea that this unit could be the result of Neolithic
739 occupation of the SW Iberian Peninsula. Palynological analyses of Neolithic sites show that,
740 since the Middle Neolithic ca. 6000 years ago, human intervention in forests in Extremadura
741 (north of the IPB) led to the formation of a savanna-like landscape, similar to that currently
742 termed “dehesa”. This kind of landscape may have been distributed to the south of Huelva,
743 including the Algarve and the Alentejo in Portugal (Stevenson and Harrison, 1992; López-Sáez
744 et al., 2005). Recent studies of core CM5 (González-Villa, 2003) indicate a significant decrease
745 in the presence of lipidic biomarkers, interpreted as indicating loss of forest mass during the
746 Neolithic period. The beginning of mining activity in the IPB in the III millennium BC (Nocete
747 et al., 2005) also generated an increase in the M/Al ratio through the last 5000 years of the
748 stratigraphic record, corresponding to the upper metres of both cores, as discussed in the next
749 section.

750

751 3.2.4. Heavy metal sedimentary record: Background levels and enrichment factors

752

753 Variations in M/Al ratios and lithological characteristics through the continuous 13kyr
754 postglacial sedimentation record from the Guadiana Estuary (cores CM5 and CM6) allow the
755 estimation of background metal concentrations from litho-stratigraphic units that were
756 unaffected by anthropogenic activities. These values are required in order to gauge whether an
757 element present in the environment has a natural origin or derives primarily from anthropogenic
758 activities (Liu et al. 2003). Based on palaeoenvironmental-lithological interpretations, we
759 considered that the *Units IV-III* (12-41m, core CM5) and *Unit VI* (24.5-47.5m, core CM6) are
760 associated with clearly estuarine and quite homogeneous sedimentation, unaffected by human
761 activities. For this reason these units were chosen to obtain natural metal concentration levels.
762 Background values (Table 4) were obtained from the mean concentrations of the elements
763 analysed in the units studied.

764 In order to analyse the impact of human activities in the last 8000 years, the metal
765 enrichment (or enrichment factor, EF) of the sediments was determined using Equation 3:

766

$$767 \quad EF = ([M] / [N])_{sample} / ([M] / [N])_{background} \quad (3)$$

768

769 Where: [M] sample = metal concentration for the studied sample, [M] background = regional
770 background, [N] sample = concentration of the normalising element for each sample, and [N]
771 background = value of the normalising element in the background.

772 The coefficient EF, which is used to estimate human impact on estuarine environments
773 (Chatterjee et al., 2007; Hwang et al., 2009), allows the concentration of a certain element to be

774 compared with the concentration expected if anthropogenic contributions of this element were
775 removed from the medium, that is, with the background value. Anthropogenic input of metals
776 may be expected when the normalised concentration of the samples is higher than background
777 levels (Hwang et al., 2009); i.e. when $EF > 1$.

778 If the EF variation is analysed on the basis of chronological periods (Fig. 9), it can be
779 observed that anthropogenic input of metals into the estuary during the Neolithic (A in Fig. 9)
780 was practically non-existent until the end of this period, when an increase in erosion (associated
781 with the Holocene thermal climatic maximum around 7000 years cal. BP) took place (Acevedo
782 et al., 2009). However, insignificant increases in EFs (Fig. 10) associated with basic rocks
783 (common in the study area) could be related to human activities. In fact, the climatic optimum
784 could have favoured the first settlements with fortifications and vine crops constructed in the
785 province of Huelva, according to an interpretation of pollen data by Chapman (2008). This
786 could have led to selective deforestation, increasing the erosion of the Guadiana Estuary's
787 bedrock. The local- to regional-scale pollution signal of some metals (e.g., Cu, Pb, and Hg) has
788 been widely linked to the earliest phase of agriculture and metallurgy in Europe during the
789 Neolithic (ca. 5800yr cal. BP) and Bronze Age (ca. 4500yr cal. BP) (Shotyk et al., 1998; Kalis
790 et al., 2003; Turney and Brown, 2007; Thevenon et al., 2011).

791 As it has been mentioned, mineral extraction in the IPB started around the Third
792 Millennium BC (e.g. Nocete et al., 2005), during the Copper Age (B in Fig. 9). These early,
793 small-scale extractions left evidence in the sedimentary record. As shown in Fig. 10, these
794 extractions could have increased the concentration of metal-sulphur (Cu, Pb and Zn) in the
795 environment. Increases in heavy metals are mirrored by increases in the enrichment of
796 lithogenic elements (Co, Cr, Ni), which are probably related to the first settlements and
797 associated anthropogenic activities, such as agriculture and deforestation. The archaeological
798 sites of João Marques in Portugal (Gonçalves, 1987) and Cabezo Juré in Spain (Nocete and
799 Linares, 1999) date from this period and provide evidence for Copper Age metallurgy. Figure 9
800 shows a generalized increase in the EF of Mn, Co, Cr, and Ni (EF values > 1) in core CM5 up
801 until the end of the Copper Age, whereas other EFs, such as those of Pb and Zn, reach values of
802 1.2 and exhibit very similar behaviour. Likewise, EF values > 1 were detected in core CM6 for
803 Co and As, whereas higher values, close to 1.5, were obtained for Pb and Mn. Recent Pb isotope
804 tests (Nocete et al., 2008) provide evidence for the exploitation of deposits in Tharsis, which
805 required deep mining. These extractions are thought to have created large-scale impacts, due to
806 deforestation, erosion, and contamination of the area, including impacts on the rivers and
807 estuaries of western Andalusia. While little evidence for Copper Age fluvio-estuarine pollution
808 has been found in sedimentary deposits from SW Andalusia, the Guadiana Estuary sediments
809 record a general increase in elements such as Co, Cr and Ni during this period.

810 Through the Early-Middle Bronze Age (3800–3200yr cal. BP), Iberian metallurgists
811 began to smelt silver for the first time. The most extensive remains (slag) have been found
812 around Rio Tinto (Pérez-Macías, 1996). In the I Millennium BC, coinciding with another
813 climate optimum (after Dansgaard et al., 1969 and Schönwiese et al., 1995), Co and Ni increase
814 significantly, and both Cu and Zn increase moderately (Fig. 10). These peaks in the EFs of Cu
815 and Zn could be the first sedimentary evidence for mining by the Tartessian civilization in the
816 SW Iberian Peninsula. The Late Bronze Age (3200–2900yr cal. BP) saw mining and metallurgy
817 flourish in the region, with strong trade networks that gradually fell under the control of
818 Phoenician merchants (Blanco et al., 1981). It appears that Copper was particularly sought after
819 by Tartessian metallurgy. Pb-isotopic tests suggest that a large number of local and regional
820 mineral deposits were exploited in search of Cu (Hunt, 2003). The Guadiana sediments from this
821 period exhibit increases in Cu enrichment factors, together with other elements commonly
822 associated with sulphide exploitation (Zn, Cd, Fe, Mn), and other elements (Co and Ni)
823 frequently associated with deforestation and bedrock erosion.

824 During the Bronze Age (C in Fig. 9), Pb shows a small decrease in EF values close to 1
825 in core CM5. Cadmium maintains its trend as described above, while elements such as Zn, Cd,
826 Cu, Co, Ni, Fe and Mn exhibit higher EF peaks (Zn \approx 1.3, Cu \approx 1.3, Co \approx 1.52, Ni \approx 1.3, Fe \approx
827 1.3 and Mn \approx 1.4), coinciding with the middle of the period (ca. 4000 years BP). A substantial
828 increase in enrichment is recorded at 3.7m (ca. 3170 years BP) for Zn (EF \approx 1.2), Cr (EF \approx 1.1),
829 Ni (EF \approx 1.4), Co (EF \approx 1.9) and Cd (EF \approx 4.3), whereas Fe and Mn reach values close to 1.
830 Bronze Age EF variations in core CM6 show trends similar to those of the earlier period
831 (Copper Age), although the lack of samples is evident. This is due to sediment infilling by a
832 high energy event, with high sand content between 7–13m depth.

833 In the VI century BC (2600yr cal. BP), activity at the Rio Tinto mine appears to have
834 declined, coinciding with the rise of the Carthaginian civilization, which became the leading
835 power in the Western Mediterranean (Pinedo Vara, 1963). This could explain a small decrease
836 in EFs for Pb and Zn, which have values close to 1 in the sedimentary record of core CM5 (Iron
837 Age: D in Fig. 9). Higher EF values were obtained for Cd (EF = 1.5), Co (EF = 1.3) and Ni (EF
838 = 1.2). The CM6 profile begins to show a general increase in EFs and has similarly high values
839 for Cd (EF = 2.1), Co (EF \approx 1.2) and Mn (EF > 1.3).

840 In the Roman period (E in Fig. 9), the general trend for the enrichment of elements is
841 maintained, and elements such as Cu (EF = 1.54), Pb (EF = 1.9), Zn (EF = 1.33) and Cd (EF >
842 3) reach maximum values in the middle or final period, whereas peaks of Co (1.52) and Ni
843 (1.47) are also evident. EFs in CM6 also have a tendency to toward an increase, and reached the
844 highest values (Pb = 1.46, Cd \approx 2, As = 1.24, Co = 1.38 and Mn = 1.9) during the middle part of
845 the period. Roman domination involved massive development in mining and metallurgy in the
846 study area, clearly registered in the EF of Cu, Pb and Zn (Fig. 10). The industry established by

847 the Romans in the area of today's Spanish provinces of Seville and Huelva and Portuguese
848 Alentejo was destined to become one of the largest mining operations in the human history
849 (Pinedo Vara, 1963).

850 During the Bronze Age and later periods (up to ca. 1800yr cal. BP), silver and gold
851 became important sources of wealth for the Phoenicians and Romans (van Geen et al., 1997).
852 This could explain increases in the enrichment of metals frequently associated with gold and
853 massive sulphide deposits, such as Pb, Zn, Cd, Mn, and Cu. Enrichment of Co, Cr, and Ni,
854 elements associated with host rocks in the lower basin of the Guadiana Estuary (Donaire et al.,
855 1998), could be linked to deforestation and open-pit mining in the past. In fact, the
856 mineralization of Co-Ni crops out as veins, which favours the leaching of these metals during
857 the weathering of massive sulphides (Almodóvar et al., 1998), either natural or influenced by
858 mining operations. Moreover, temperature and rainfall anomalies (Fig. 10) in certain periods
859 (Late Iron Age or post-Roman migration period suggested by Büntgen et al., 2011) do not show
860 any relation with Co, Cr and Ni EFs, thus pointing to a preferential anthropogenic influence. At
861 the end of Roman period and during the early post-Roman period (II century AD, 1800yr cal.
862 BP), the concentrations of all elements tend to decrease, approaching and even reaching
863 background values. According to Berglund (2003), heavy metal fluxes continuously decrease
864 following the decline of the Roman Empire (ca. 400 AD), and remain low during the subsequent
865 cold "Migration period" (Fig.10), which is known as a period of land abandonment and
866 reforestation in Northwest Europe. According to Davis et al. (2000), the cultures that followed
867 the Roman period (1600–500yr cal. BP) essentially abandoned mining operations in SW Iberia.

868 Our data indicate that from ca. 1200yr cal. BP, coinciding with the Medieval Period, a
869 gradual increase in some elements occurs. This increase in EFs is clearly related to another
870 climatic optimum and the expansion of medieval metallurgy, which could be related to the
871 intensive production of armaments (Fig. 10). In this respect, Figure 9 shows that mainly Pb
872 (1.64), Zn (\approx 1.6), As (\approx 1.3), Cd (\approx 1.5), Co (1.6), and Ni (1.7) present maximum enrichment
873 values associated with high Mn enrichment (\approx 6). This may reflect the beginning of modern
874 mining in the Lower Basin of the Guadiana Estuary, given that the volcanic sedimentary
875 successions of the IPB contain a large number of Manganese mineral occurrences (Fernández-
876 Caliani et al., 2008). Some authors (e.g. Salkield, 1987) have suggested that these deposits were
877 exploited on a small scale since pre-Roman times. The depletion in Mn EF in the CM6 record at
878 the beginning of post-Roman period is less obvious and a general increase in EF for Pb (\approx 1.7),
879 Mn (\approx 1.75) and in less extent Co (\approx 1.4), Ni (\approx 1.3) is observed.

880 In more recent times, ranging from late Medieval times to the present (Modern time:
881 Fig. 9), a short and abrupt decline in anthropogenic trace metal deposition between 800-500yr
882 cal. BP (Thevenon et al., 2011) occurred. This period, clearly depicted in Fig. 10, saw the
883 occurrence of the Great Famine and one of the deadliest pandemics in human history, the Black

884 Death, peaking in Europe between 1346 and 1353 AD (Hays, 2005). Additionally, a small
885 depletion of EF is observed ca. 200yr BP, probably related to a modern migration period
886 (Büntgen et al., 2011). While an overall increase of Pb (1.84), Zn (2.47), As (1.77), Cd (1.94)
887 and Cu (1.86) has continued in both cores since 200 year BP, other elements, such as Co (1.08),
888 Cr (0.96), Ni (0.92) and Mn, have returned to natural levels, according to the result obtained by
889 Delgado et al. (2010) for surficial sediments.

890

891 **4. Conclusions**

892

893 Sedimentological, foraminiferal and diatom analyses of core material from two deep
894 boreholes enabled the palaeoenvironmental reconstruction of the Guadiana River Estuary during
895 postglacial sea-level rise. These data were complemented by the results of our previous studies
896 in 3 other boreholes from the same estuary and allowed the elaboration of a local sea-level
897 curve. The transition from fluvial to estuarine sedimentation in Guadiana River Estuary began
898 around 13.3kyr cal. BP and was halted during the Younger Dryas stadial. From beginning of the
899 Holocene until the mid-Holocene the sea-level rose at a rate close to $7\text{mm}\cdot\text{yr}^{-1}$. Although this
900 figure could be even higher during the period 8500–7500yr cal. BP, the evidence is based on
901 dated shells from the estuarine channel facies and therefore requires further confirmation. From
902 the mid-Holocene to the present, the rate of sea-level rise decelerated to $1.8\text{mm}\cdot\text{yr}^{-1}$. The
903 age/depth relation for that period is less linear than the previous phase, because sedimentation
904 was not synchronous at all the 5 sites due to reduced sediment accommodation space.

905 Factor Analysis highlights three associations between elements. *Group I* principally
906 includes major elements, metals, and some other trace elements related to clay minerals. The
907 distribution of factor scores points to a dual origin for this group: a natural origin as a
908 constituent of phyllosilicates and an anthropogenic origin characterized by an increase in factor
909 scores through the last 4500 years, probably due to the mining activities in the IPB. *Group II*
910 (Fe, Mg, Ca, Sr Na, LOI, TC, TS, As, Cd, and Cu) is of essentially natural origin, associated
911 with the marine fauna present in the record and with diagenetic processes that provoke the
912 oxidation of pyrite and the precipitation of secondary carbonate minerals. *Group III* (Mn, Cd,
913 Co, Ni, Pb, Zn, and Cu) consists of strongly correlated elements in the top section of the cores,
914 revealing that they are clearly associated with mining activities.

915 M/Al ratios, together with the lithostratigraphic characteristics of the postglacial
916 sedimentary record, enable us to identify units typical of tidal environments unaffected by
917 anthropogenic activities and therefore establish background levels of element concentrations.
918 Significant enrichment of Mn, Pb, Zn, Cd, Co, Ni, and Cu are recorded through the last 4500
919 years. Cu, Pb and Zn are clearly derived from anthropogenic activities and correlated with the
920 exploitation of sulphide deposits in the area, while Co and Ni are probably enriched as a

921 consequence of deforestation linked to prehistoric settlements in general and to mining
922 operations in particular. Levels of other elements such as Fe and As have remained practically
923 unaltered.

924 The palaeoenvironmental reconstruction of the Guadiana Estuary (and, by extension, of
925 the SW Iberian Peninsula) based on EF profiles distinguishes five historical stages: 1) the
926 Holocene climate optimum around 7000yr cal. BP, when the supply of trace metals to the
927 estuary was due to natural processes, and four stages (Anthropocene period) in which
928 anthropogenic inputs of metals prevailed over natural sources in the sedimentary record: 2) the
929 commencement of mining in the Iberian Pyrite Belt in the III Millennium BC, around 4500
930 years ago (since the beginning of the Copper Age); 3) the rise of Tartessos in the I Millennium
931 BC; 4) the height of the Roman Empire (2000yr cal. BP), when mining activities became
932 particularly intensive; and 5) the last 1200yr cal. BP, during which modern mining activities in
933 the Iberian Pyrite Belt intensified.

934 Our analysis of the sedimentological and geochemical characteristics of postglacial
935 infill in the Guadiana Estuary has revealed valuable information from a palaeo-
936 environmental/historical perspective. Combining marine (radiocarbon age) and environmental
937 (metal enrichment) proxies informed about the sea-level changes and the anthropogenic impact
938 in the study area. Moreover, it has allowed us to better understand the factors which control the
939 behaviour of the metals responsible for contamination in estuarine environments historically
940 affected by acid mine drainage.

941

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943

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950

951 **References**

952

- 953 Ackermann, F., 1980. A procedure for correcting the grain size effect in heavy metal analyses
954 of estuarine and coastal sediments. *Environmental Technology Letters* 1(11), 518-527.
- 955 Allen, H.D., 2003. A transient coastal wetland: from estuarine to supratidal conditions in less
956 than 2000 years e Boca do Rio, Algarve, Portugal. *Land Degradation and Development*
957 14, 265-283.

- 958 Almodóvar, G.R., Sáez, R., Pons, U.M., Maestre, A., Toscano, M., Pascual, E., 1998. Geology
959 and genesis of the Aznalcollar massive sulphide deposits, Iberian Pyrite Belt, Spain.
960 Mineral. Deposita 33, 111-136.
- 961 Aloupi, M., Angelidis, M.O., 2001. Geochemistry of natural and anthropogenic metals in the
962 coastal sediments of the island of Lesbos, Aegean Sea. Environmental Pollution 113(2),
963 211-219.
- 964 Álvarez-Valero, A.M., Pérez-López, R., Matos, J., Capitán, M.A., Nieto, J.M., Sáez, R.,
965 Delgado, J., Caraballo, M., 2008. Potential environmental impact at Sao Domingos
966 mining district (Iberian Pyrite Belt, SW Iberian Peninsula): Evidence from a chemical
967 and mineralogical characterization. Environmental Geology 55(8), 1797-1809.
- 968 Andrade, C., Freitas, M.C., Moreno, J., Craveiro, S.C., 2004. Stratigraphical evidence of Late
969 Holocene barrier breaching and extreme storms in lagoonal sediments of Ria Formosa,
970 Algarve, Portugal. Marine Geology 210, 339–362.
- 971 Ayyamperumal, T., Jonathan, M.P., Srinivasalu, S., Armstrong-Altrin, J.S., Ram-Mohan, V.,
972 2006. Assessment of acid leachable trace metals in sediment cores from River Uppanar,
973 Cuddalore, Southeast coast of India. Environmental Pollution 143(1), 34-45.
- 974 Azevêdo, T.M., Gonçalves, A., 2009. Geochemistry of core sediments from the Middle Tagus
975 alluvial plain (Portugal) since the last glacial: using background determination methods
976 to outline environmental changes. Environmental Earth Sciences 59, 191–204.
- 977 Bailey, G.N., Flemming, N., 2008. Archaeology of the continental shelf: Marine resources,
978 submerged landscapes and underwater archaeology. Quaternary Science Reviews 27,
979 2153-2165.
- 980 Baker, D., Peterson, C., Hemphill-Haley, E., Twichell, D., 2010. Latest Pleistocene and
981 Holocene (2-16ka) sedimentation in the Columbia River Estuary, Oregon, USA. Marine
982 Geology 273 (1-4), 44-61.
- 983 Bard E, Hamelin B, Delanghe-Sabatier D., 2010. Deglacial melt water pulse 1B and Younger
984 Dryas sea-levels revisited with new onshore boreholes at Tahiti. Science 327, 1235-
985 1237.
- 986 Bard, E., Hamelin, B., Arnold, M., Montaggioni, L., Cabloch, G., Faure, G., Rougerie, F., 1996.
987 Deglacial sea-level record from Tahiti corals and the timing of global meltwater
988 discharge. Nature 382 (6588), 241-244.
- 989 Berglund, B.E., 2003. Human impact and climate changes - synchronous events and a causal
990 link?. Quaternary International 105, 7-12.
- 991 Bertine, K.K., Goldberg, E.D., 1977. History of heavy metal pollution in southern California
992 coastal zone - reprise. Environmental Science and Technology 11(3), 297-299.
- 993 Blanco, A., Rothemberg, B., 1981. Exploración Arqueometalúrgica de Huelva. Ed. Labor, S.A.
994 Barcelona, Spain.

- 995 Blomqvist S., Larsson U., and Borg H. (1992) Heavy metal decrease in the sediments of a
996 Baltic bay following tertiary sewage treatment. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 24(5), 258-
997 266.
- 998 Borrego, J., López-González, N., Carro, B., 2004. Geochemical signature as
999 palaeoenvironmental markers in Holocene sediments of the Tinto River estuary
1000 (Southwestern Spain). *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 61(4), 631-641.
- 1001 Borrego, J., Ruiz, F., González-Regalado, M.L., Pendón, J.G., Morales, J.A., 1999. The
1002 Holocene transgression into the estuarine central basin of the Odiel River mouth (Cadiz
1003 Gulf, SW, Spain): lithology and faunal assemblages. *Quaternary Science Reviews*
1004 18(6), 769-788.
- 1005 Boski, T., Camacho, S., Moura, D., Fletcher, W., Wilamowski, A., Veiga-Pires, C., Correia, V.,
1006 Loureiro, C., Santana, P., 2008. Chronology of the sedimentary processes during the
1007 postglacial sea level rise in two estuaries of the Algarve coast, Southern Portugal.
1008 *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 77(2), 230-244.
- 1009 Boski, T., Moura, D., Veiga-Pires, C., Camacho, S., Duarte, D., Scott, D.B., Fernandes, S.G.,
1010 2002. Postglacial sea-level rise and sedimentary response in the Guadiana Estuary,
1011 Portugal/Spain border. *Sedimentary Geology* 150(1-2), 103-122.
- 1012 Büntgen, U., Tegel, W., Nicolussi, K., McCormick, M., Frank, D., Trouet, V., Kaplan, J.O.,
1013 Herzig, F., Heussner, K.-U., Wanner, H., Luterbacher, J.r., Esper, J., 2011. 2500 years
1014 of European climate variability and human susceptibility. *Science* 331, 578-582.
- 1015 Cantwell, M.G., King, J.W., Burgess, R.M., Appleby, P.G., 2007. Reconstruction of
1016 contaminant trends in a salt wedge estuary with sediment cores dated using a multiple
1017 proxy approach. *Marine Environmental Research* 64(2), 225-246.
- 1018 Carral, E., Villares, R., Puente, X., Carballeira, A., 1995. Influence of watershed lithology on
1019 heavy metal levels in estuarine sediments and organisms in Galicia (north-west Spain).
1020 *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 30(9), 604-608.
- 1021 Chapman, R., 2008. Producing inequalities: regional sequences in later prehistoric southern
1022 Spain. *World Prehist* 21, 195–260.
- 1023 Chatterjee, M., Silva Filho, E.V., Sarkar, S.K., Sella, S.M., Bhattacharya, A., Satpathy, K.K.,
1024 Prasad, M.V.R., Chakraborty, S., Bhattacharya, B.D., 2007. Distribution and possible
1025 source of trace elements in the sediment cores of a tropical macrotidal estuary and their
1026 ecotoxicological significance. *Environment International* 33(3), 346-356.
- 1027 Chester, D.K., James, P.A., 1991. Holocene alluviation in the Algarve, southern Portugal: the
1028 case for an anthropogenic cause. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 18, 73-87.
- 1029 Clarke, G.K.C., Leverington, D.W., Teller, J.T., Dyke, A.S., 2004. Palaeohydraulics of the last
1030 outburst flood from glacial Lake Agassiz and the 8200 BP cold event. *Quaternary*
1031 *Science Reviews* 23, 389–407.

- 1032 Cobelo-García, A., Prego, R., 2003. Heavy metal sedimentary record in a Galician Ria (NW
1033 Spain): background values and recent contamination. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 46(10),
1034 1253-1262.
- 1035 Cohen, M.N., 1977. *The food Crisis in Prehistory: Overpopulation and origins of agriculture.*
1036 Yale University Press, New Haven, 342 p.
- 1037 Covelli, S., Fontolan, G., Faganeli, J., Ogrinc, N., 2006. Anthropogenic markers in the
1038 Holocene stratigraphic sequence of the Gulf of Trieste (northern Adriatic Sea). *Marine*
1039 *Geology* 230(1-2), 29-51.
- 1040 Cundy, A.B. Croudace, I.W., 1996. Sedimentary and geochemical variations in a salt
1041 marsh/mud flat environment from the mesotidal Hamble estuary, southern England.
1042 *Marine Chemistry* 51(2), 115-132.
- 1043 Dabrio, C.J., Zazo, C., Goy, J.L., Sierro, F.J., Borja, F., Lario, J., Gonzalez, J.A., Flores, J.A.,
1044 2000. Depositional history of estuarine infill during the last postglacial transgression
1045 (Gulf of Cadiz, Southern Spain). *Marine Geology* 162(2-4), 381-404.
- 1046 Daskalakis, K.D., O'Connor, T.P., 1995. Normalization and elemental sediment contamination
1047 in the coastal United States. *Environmental Science and Technology* 29(2), 470-477.
- 1048 Davis Jr, R.A., Welty, A.T., Borrego, J., Morales, J.A., Pendón, J.G., Ryan, J.G., 2000, Rio
1049 Tinto estuary (Spain): 5000 years of pollution. *Environmental Geology* 39(10), 1107-
1050 1116.
- 1051 Dean, R.M., Valente, M.J., Carvalho, A.F., 2011. The Mesolithic / Neolithic transition on the
1052 Costa Vicentina, Portugal. *Quaternary International*, doi:10.1016/j.quaint.2011.10.024.
- 1053 Delgado, J., Barba-Brioso, C., Nieto, J.M., Boski, T., 2011. Speciation and ecological risk of
1054 toxic elements in estuarine sediments affected by multiple anthropogenic contributions
1055 (Guadiana saltmarshes, SW Iberian Peninsula): I. Surficial sediments. *Science of the*
1056 *Total Environment* 409, 3666-3679.
- 1057 Delgado, J., Nieto, J.M., Boski, T., 2010. Analysis of the spatial variation of heavy metals in the
1058 Guadiana Estuary sediments (SW Iberian Peninsula) based on GIS-mapping techniques.
1059 *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 88, 71-83.
- 1060 Delgado, J., Sarmiento, A., Condesso de Melo, M., Nieto, J., 2009. Environmental Impact of
1061 Mining Activities in the Southern Sector of the Guadiana Basin (SW of the Iberian
1062 Peninsula). *Water, Air, and Soil Pollution* 199(1), 323-341.
- 1063 Dias J.M.A, Boski T., Rodrigues, A., Magalhães F., 2000. Coast line evolution in Portugal since
1064 the Last Glacial Maximum until Present - A synthesis. *Marine Geology* 170, 17-186.
- 1065 Donaire, T., Sáez, R., Pascual, E., 1998. Geología y evolución magmática del eje volcánico de
1066 Paymogo, Faja Pirítica Ibérica. *Geogaceta* 24, 115-118.

- 1067 Fa, D.A., 2008. Effects of tidal amplitude on intertidal resource availability and dispersal
1068 pressure in prehistoric human coastal populations: the Mediterranean-Atlantic
1069 transition. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 27, 2194-2209.
- 1070 Fairbanks, R.G., 1989. A 17,000-year glacio-eustatic sea level record: Influence of glacial
1071 melting rates on the Younger Dryas event and deep-ocean circulation. *Nature* 342, 637-
1072 642.
- 1073 Fatela, F., Taborda, R., 2001. Confidence limits of species proportions in microfossil
1074 assemblage. *Marine Micropaleontology* 45, 169-174.
- 1075 Fernández-Caliani, J.C., Barba-Brioso, C., González, I., Galán, E., 2009. Heavy metal pollution
1076 in soils around the abandoned mine sites of the Iberian Pyrite Belt (Southwest Spain).
1077 *Water, Air, and Soil Pollution* 200, 211–226.
- 1078 Fernández-Caliani, J.C., Muñoz, F.R., Galán, E., 1997. Clay mineral and heavy metal
1079 distributions in the lower estuary of Huelva and adjacent Atlantic shelf, SW Spain.
1080 *Science of the Total Environment* 198(2), 181-200.
- 1081 Fischer, A., Olsen, J., Richards, M., Heinemeier, J., Sveinbjornsdottir, A.E., Bennike, P., 2007.
1082 Coast-inland mobility and diet in the Danish Mesolithic and Neolithic: evidence from
1083 stable isotope values of humans and dogs. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 34 (12),
1084 2125-2150.
- 1085 Fletcher, W.J., Boski, T., Moura, D., 2007. Palynological evidence for environmental and
1086 climatic changes in the lower Guadiana valley (Portugal) during the last 13,000 years.
1087 *The Holocene* 17, 479-492.
- 1088 Galili, E.N.Y., 1993. The submerged pre-pottery Neolithic water well of Atlit-Yam, northern
1089 Israel and its palaeoenvironmental implications. *The Holocene*, 3, 265-270.
- 1090 García-García, A., García-Gil, S., Vilas, F., 2005. Quaternary evolution of the Ria de Vigo,
1091 Spain. *Marine Geology* 220, 153-179.
- 1092 Garel, E., Pinto, L., Santos, A., Ferreira, O., 2009. Tidal and river discharge forcing upon water
1093 and sediment circulation at a rock-bound estuary (Guadiana estuary, Portugal).
1094 *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 84, 269-281.
- 1095 Gomonçalves, V., 1987. Megalitismo e Metalurgia no Alto Algarve Oriental. Uma aproximação
1096 integrada. Lisboa, Portugal.
- 1097 González-Vila, F.J., Polvillo, O., Boski, T., Moura, D., de Andres, J.R., 2003. Biomarker
1098 patterns in a time-resolved Holocene/terminal Pleistocene sedimentary sequence from
1099 the Guadiana river estuarine area (SW Portugal/Spain border). *Organic Geochemistry*
1100 34(12), 1601-1613.
- 1101 González, R., Araújo, M.F., Burdloff, D., Cachão, M., Cascalho, J., Correadeira, C., Dias,
1102 J.M.A., Fradique, C., Ferreira, J., Gomes, C., Machado, A., Mendes, I., Rocha, F., 2007.

- 1103 Sediment and pollutant transport in the Northern Gulf of Cadiz: A multi-proxy
1104 approach. *Journal of Marine Systems* 68(1-2), 1-23.
- 1105 Goy, J.L., Zazo, C., Dabrio, C.J., Lario, J., Borja, F., Sierro, F.J., Flores, J.A., 1996. Global and
1106 regional factors controlling changes of coastlines in Southern Iberia (Spain) during the
1107 Holocene. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 15, 773-780.
- 1108 Grousset, F.E., Quetel, C.R., Thomas, B., Donard, O.F., Lambert, C.E., Guillard, F., Monaco,
1109 A., 1995. Anthropogenic vs. lithogenic origins of trace elements (As, Cd, Pb, Rb, Sb,
1110 Sc, Sn, Zn) in water column particles: Northwestern Mediterranean Sea. *Marine*
1111 *Chemistry* 48(3-4), 291-310.
- 1112 Gulliksen, S., Birks, H.H., Possnert, G., Mangerud, J., 1998. A calendar age estimate of the
1113 Younger Dryas Holocene boundary at Krakenes, western Norway. *The Holocene* 8,
1114 249-259.
- 1115 Hartmann, P.C., Quinn, J.G., Cairns, R.W., King, J.W., 2005. Depositional history of organic
1116 contaminants in Narragansett Bay, Rhode Island, USA. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 50(4),
1117 388-395.
- 1118 Hays, J.N., 2005. *Epidemics and pandemics: their impacts on human history*. 513 p. ISBN
1119 1851096582.
- 1120 Herut, B., Hornung, H., Krom, M.D., Kress, N., Cohen, Y., 1993. Trace metals in shallow
1121 sediments from the Mediterranean coastal region of Israel. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*
1122 26(12), 675-682.
- 1123 Hijma, M.P., Cohen, K.M., 2010. Timing and magnitude of the sea-level jump precluding the
1124 8200 yr event. *Geology* 38 (3), 275-278.
- 1125 Hindson, R.A., Andrade, C., 1999. Sedimentation and hydrodynamic processes associated with
1126 the tsunami generated by the 1755 Lisbon earthquake. *Quaternary International* 56, 27–
1127 38.
- 1128 Hunt, M.A., 2003. Prehistoric mining and metallurgy in south west Iberian Peninsula. *British*
1129 *Archaeological Reports International Series* 1188, Oxford.
- 1130 Hwang, H.M., Green, P., Young, T., 2009. Historical trends of trace metals in a sediment core
1131 from a contaminated tidal salt marsh in San Francisco Bay. *Environmental*
1132 *Geochemistry and Health* 31(4), 421-430.
- 1133 Jolliffe, T., 2002. *Principal Component Analysis*. Series: Springer Series in Statistics 2nd ed.,
1134 XXIX, 487 p.
- 1135 Kaiser, H.F. 1958. The varimax criterion for analytic rotation in factor analysis, *Psychometrika*
1136 23, 187-200.
- 1137 Kalis, A.J., Merkt, J., Wunderlich, J., 2003. Environmental changes during the Holocene
1138 climatic optimum in central Europe-human impact and natural causes. *Quaternary*
1139 *Science Reviews* 22 (1), 33-79.

- 1140 Katahira, K., Ishitake, M., Moriwaki, H., Yamamoto, O., Fujita, T., Yamazaki, H., Yoshikawa,
1141 S., 2009. Statistical analysis of metal concentrations in a sediment core to reveal
1142 influences of human activities on atmospheric environment for 200 years. *Water, Air,
1143 and Soil Pollution* 204(1), 215-225.
- 1144 Kortekaas, S., Dawson, A.G., 2007. Distinguishing tsunami and storm deposits: an example
1145 from Martinhal, SW Portugal. *Sedimentary Geology* 200, 208–221.
- 1146 Leblanc, M., Morales, J.A., Borrego, J., Elbaz-Poulichet, F., 2000. 4,500-year-old mining
1147 pollution in southwestern Spain: Long-term implications for modern mining pollution.
1148 *Economic Geology* 95(3), 655-661.
- 1149 Lee, S.V. Cundy, A.B., 2001. Heavy metal contamination and mixing processes in sediments
1150 from the Humber Estuary, Eastern England. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 53(5),
1151 619-636.
- 1152 Liu, J., Saito, Y., Kong, X., Wang, H., Xiang, L., Wen, C., Nakashima, R., 2010. Sedimentary
1153 record of environmental evolution off the Yangtze River estuary, East China Sea,
1154 during the last ~13,000 years, with special reference to the influence of the Yellow
1155 River on the Yangtze River delta during the last 600 years. *Quaternary Science Reviews*
1156 29 (17-18), 2424-2438.
- 1157 Liu, W.X., Li, X.D., Shen, Z.G., Wang, D.C., Wai, O.W.H., Li, Y.S., 2003. Multivariate
1158 statistical study of heavy metal enrichment in sediments of the Pearl River Estuary.
1159 *Environmental Pollution* 121(3), 377-388.
- 1160 López-González, N., Borrego, J., Ruiz, F., Carro, B., Lozano-Soria, O., Abad, M., 2006.
1161 Geochemical variations in estuarine sediments: Provenance and environmental changes
1162 (Southern Spain). *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 67(1-2), 313-320.
- 1163 López-Sáenz, J.A., López-García, P., López-Merino, L., Cerrillo-Cuenca, E., González-
1164 Cordero, A., Prada, A., 2005. Prehistoric landscapes in North Extremadura between the
1165 VIth and the IVth millennia cal. BC. *Journal of Iberian Archaeology* 7, 23-35.
- 1166 Loring, D.H., 1991. Normalization of heavy-metal data from estuarine and coastal sediments.
1167 *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 48(1), 101-115.
- 1168 Loring, D.H., Rantala, R.T.T., 1992. Manual for the geochemical analyses of marine sediments
1169 and suspended particulate matter. *Earth-Science Reviews* 32(4), 235-283.
- 1170 Mannino, M.A., Thomas, K.D., 2001. Extensive Mesolithic exploitation of coastal resources?
1171 Evidence from a shell deposit on the Isle of Portland (Southern England) for the impact
1172 of human foraging on populations of intertidal rocky shore molluscs. *Journal of
1173 Archaeological Science* 28 (10), 1101-1114.
- 1174 Matos, J., Pereira, Z., Oliveira, V., Oliveira, J.T., 2002. The geological setting of the São
1175 Domingos pyrite orebody, Iberian Pyrite Belt. VII Congresso Nacional de Geologia, 1-
1176 4.

- 1177 Mil-Homens, M., Stevens, R.L., Abrantes, F., Cato, I., 2006. Heavy metal assessment for
1178 surface sediments from three areas of the Portuguese continental shelf. *Continental*
1179 *Shelf Research* 26(10), 1184-1205.
- 1180 Morales, J.A., 1993. *Sedimentología del Estuario del Río Guadiana (SO España-Portugal)*.
1181 Doctoral Tesis, University of Sevilla, 300 pp.
- 1182 Morales, J.A., Borrego, J., San Miguel, E.G., López-González, N., Carro, B., 2008. Sedimentary
1183 record of recent tsunamis in the Huelva Estuary (southwestern Spain). *Quaternary*
1184 *Science Reviews* 27(7-8), 734-746.
- 1185 Morillo, J., Usero, J., Gracia, I., 2004. Heavy metal distribution in marine sediments from the
1186 southwest coast of Spain. *Chemosphere* 55(3), 431-442.
- 1187 Moura, D., Veiga-Pires, C., Albardeiro, L., Boski, T., Rodrigues, A.L., Tareco, H., 2007.
1188 Holocene sea level fluctuations and coastal evolution in the central Algarve (southern
1189 Portugal). *Marine Geology* 237, 127-142.
- 1190 Nocete, F., Alex, E., Nieto, J.M., Sáez, R., Bayona, M.R., 2005. An archaeological approach to
1191 regional environmental pollution in the south-western Iberian Peninsula related to third
1192 millennium BC mining and metallurgy. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 32(10),
1193 1566-1576.
- 1194 Nocete, F., Linares, J.A., 1999. "Las primeras sociedades mineras en Huelva. Alosno". En
1195 *Historia de la provincia de Huelva*, cap. 4, 50-64. *Diario Huelva Información*, Huelva,
1196 Spain.
- 1197 Nocete, F., Queipo, G., Sáez, R., Nieto, J.M., Inácio, N., Bayona, M.R., 2008. The smelting
1198 quarter of Valencina del la Concepción (Seville, Spain): The specialised copper industry
1199 in a political centre of the Guadalquivir valley during the third millennium BC (2750-
1200 2500 BC). *Journal of Archaeological Science* 35, 717-732.
- 1201 Pavlopoulos, K., Triantaphyllou, M., Karkanias, P., Kouli, K., Syrides, G., Vouvalidis, K.,
1202 Palyvos, N., Tsourou, T., 2010. Paleoenvironmental evolution and prehistoric human
1203 environment, in the embayment of Palamari (Skyros Island, Greece) during Middle-
1204 Late Holocene. *Quaternary International* 216, 41-53.
- 1205 Peltier, W. R., Fairbanks, R. G., 2006. Global glacial ice volume and Last Glacial Maximum
1206 duration from an extended Barbados sea level record. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 25,
1207 3322-3337.
- 1208 Pérez-Macías, J.A., 1996. *Metalurgia extractiva prerromana en Huelva*. Servicio de
1209 Publicaciones de la Universidad de Huelva. Huelva, Spain.
- 1210 Pinedo Vara, I., 1963. *Piritas de Huelva. Su historia, minería y aprovechamiento*. Ed. Summa.
1211 Madrid, Spain. 1003 pp.
- 1212 Piper, D.Z., 1971. The distribution of Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni and Zn in Framverren, a
1213 Norwegian anoxic Fjord. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* 35, 531-559.

- 1214 Polvillo, O., González-Pérez, J. A., Boski, T., González-Vila, F.J., 2009. Structural features of
1215 humic acids from a sedimentary sequence in the Guadiana estuary (Portugal-Spain
1216 border). *Organic Geochemistry* 40(1), 20-28.
- 1217 Price, G.D., Winkle, K., Gehrels, W.R. 2005. A geochemical record of the mining history of the
1218 Erme Estuary, south Devon, UK. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 50(12), 1706-1712.
- 1219 Rae, J.E., 1997. Trace metals in deposited intertidal sediments. In: Jickells, T.D., Rae, J.E.
1220 (Eds.), *Biogeochemistry of Intertidal Sediments*. Cambridge University Press,
1221 Cambridge, 16-41.
- 1222 Reimer, P.J., Baillie, M.G.L., Bard, E., Bayliss, A., Beck, J.W., Blackwell, P.G., Bronk-
1223 Ramsey, C., Buck, C.E., Burr, G.S., Edwards, R.L., Friedrich, M., Grootes, P.M.,
1224 Guilderson, T.P., Hajdas, I., Heaton, T.J., Hogg, A.G., Hughen, K.A., Kaiser, K.F.,
1225 Kromer, B., McCormac, F.G., Manning, S.W., Reimer, R.W., Richards, D.A., Southon,
1226 J.R., Talamo, S., Turney, C.S.M., van der Plicht, J., Weyhenmeyer, C.E., 2009.
1227 IntCal09 and Marine09 radiocarbon age calibration curves, 0–50,000 years cal BP.
1228 *Radiocarbon* 51(4): 1111–50.
- 1229 Rodrigues, T., Grimalt, J.O., Abrantes, F., Naughton, F., Flores, J.-A. 2010. The last glacial-
1230 interglacial transition (LGIT) in the western mid-latitudes of the North Atlantic: Abrupt
1231 sea surface temperature change and sea level implications. *Quaternary Science Reviews*
1232 29 (15-16), 1853-1862.
- 1233 Rodríguez-Ramírez, A., Yáñez-Camacho, C.M., 2008. Formation of chenier plain of Doñana
1234 marshland (SW Spain): observation and geomorphic model. *Marine Geology* 254, 187-
1235 196.
- 1236 Rolett, B.V., Zheng, Z., Yue, Y. (2011) Holocene sea-level change and the emergence of
1237 Neolithic seafaring in the Fuzhou Basin (Fujian, China). *Quaternary Science Reviews*
1238 30 (7-8), 788-797
- 1239 Round, F.E., Crawford, R.M., Mann, D.G., 1990. *The Diatoms, Biology and Morphology of the*
1240 *Genera*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge. 747 pp.
- 1241 Ruiz, F., 2001. Trace Metals in Estuarine Sediments from the Southwestern Spanish Coast.
1242 *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 42(6), 481-489.
- 1243 Ruiz, F., Borrego, J., López-González, N., Abad, M., González-Regalado, M., Carro, B., Pendón,
1244 J.G., Rodríguez-Vidal, J., Cáceres, L.M., Prudêncio, M.I., Dias, M.I., 2007. The
1245 geological record of a mid-Holocene marine storm in southwestern Spain. *Geo-bios* 40,
1246 689-699.
- 1247 Ruiz, F., González-Regalado, M.L., Morales, J.A., 1996. Distribución y ecología de los
1248 foraminiferainíferos y ostrácodos actuales del estuario mesomareal del Río Guadiana
1249 (S.O. España). *Geobios* 29 (5), 513-528.

- 1250 Ruiz, F., Rodríguez-Ramírez, A., Cáceres, L M., Rodríguez-Vidal, J., Carretero, M.I., Abad,
1251 M., Pozo, M., 2005. Evidence of high-energy events in the geological record: Mid-
1252 Holocene evolution of the southwestern Doñana National Park (SW Spain).
1253 *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 229, 212–229.
- 1254 Sáez, R., Pascual, E., Toscano, M., Almodóvar, G.R. 1999. The Iberian type of volcano-
1255 sedimentary massive sulphide deposits. *Mineralium Deposita* 34(5-6), 549-570.
- 1256 Salkield, L.U., 1987. A technical history of the Rio Tinto Mines. Some Notes on exploitation
1257 from Pre-Phoenician times to the 1950s. Institution of Mining and Metallurgy, London.
- 1258 Sanger, D.M., Holland, A.F., Scott, G.I. 1999. Tidal creek and salt marsh sediments in South
1259 Carolina coastal estuaries: I. Distribution of trace metals. *Archives of Environmental*
1260 *Contamination and Toxicology* 37(4), 445-457.
- 1261 Schneider, H., Höfer, D., Trog, C., Busch, S., Schneider, M., Baade, J., Daut, G., Mäusbacher,
1262 R., 2010. Holocene estuary development in the Algarve Region (Southern Portugal) - A
1263 reconstruction of sedimentological and ecological evolution. *Quaternary International*
1264 221, 141–158
- 1265 Scott, D.B., Hermelin, J.O.R., 1993. A device for precision splitting of micropaleontological
1266 samples in liquid suspension. *Journal of Paleontology* 67, 151-154.
- 1267 Shotyk, W., Weiss, D., Appleby, P.G., Cheburkin, A.K., Frei, R., Gloor, M., Kramers, J.D.,
1268 Reese, S., van der Knaap, W.O., 1998. History of atmospheric lead deposition since
1269 12,370 ¹⁴C yr BP recorded in a peat bog profile, Jura Mountains, Switzerland. *Science*
1270 281, 1635-1640.
- 1271 Simancas, J.F., Pérez Estaún, A., 2004. Evolución tectónica del Macizo Ibérico. In: *Geología de*
1272 *España* (J.A. Vera, Ed.), chapter 2 (Macizo Ibérico; Pérez Estaún, A. and Bea, F., Eds)
1273 SGE-IGME, Madrid, 224-230.
- 1274 Smith, D.E., S. Harrison, Firth, C.R., Jordan, J.T., 2011. The early Holocene sea level rise,
1275 *Quaternary Science Reviews* 30, 1846-1860.
- 1276 Spencer, K.L., Cundy, A.B., Croudace, I.W., 2003. Heavy metal distribution and early-
1277 diagenesis in salt marsh sediments from the Medway Estuary, Kent, UK. *Estuarine,*
1278 *Coastal and Shelf Science* 57(1-2), 43-54.
- 1279 Stanley, D.J., Warne, A.G., 1994. Worldwide initiation of holocene marine deltas
1280 by deceleration of sea-level rise. *Science* 265, 228-231.
- 1281 Stecko, J.R.P., Bendell-Young, L.I., 2000. Contrasting the geochemistry of suspended
1282 particulate matter and deposited sediments within an estuary. *Applied Geochemistry*
1283 15(6), 753-775.
- 1284 Stuiver, M., Reimer, P.J., Reimer, R.W., 2009. CALIB 6.0. Internet Program and
1285 Documentation.

- 1286 Thevenon, F., Guédron, S., Chiaradia, M., Loizeau, J., Poté, J., 2011. (Pre-) historic changes in
1287 natural and anthropogenic heavy metals deposition inferred from two contrasting Swiss
1288 Alpine lakes. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 30, 224-233.
- 1289 Tjallingii, R., Stattegger, K., Wetzel, A., Van Phach, P., 2010. Infilling and flooding of the
1290 Mekong River incised valley during deglacial sea-level rise. *Quaternary Science*
1291 *Reviews* 29, 1432-1444.
- 1292 Turney, C.S.M., Brown, H., 2007. Catastrophic early Holocene sea level rise, human migration
1293 and the Neolithic transition in Europe. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 26, 2036-2041.
- 1294 Van der Schriek, T., Passmore, D.G., Rolao, J., Stevenson, A.C., 2007. Estuarine–fluvial
1295 floodplain formation in the Holocene Lower Tagus valley (Central Portugal) and
1296 implications for Quaternary fluvial system evolution. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 26,
1297 2937–2957.
- 1298 Van Geen, A., Adkins, J.F., Boyle, E.A., Nelson, C.H., Palanques, A., 1997. A 120-yr record of
1299 widespread contamination from mining of the Iberian pyrite belt. *Geology* 25(4), 291-
1300 294.
- 1301 Viguri, J.R., Irabien, M.J., Yusta, I., Soto, J., Gomez, J., Rodriguez, P., Martinez-Madrid, M.,
1302 Irabien, J.A., Coz, A., 2007. Physico-chemical and toxicological characterization of the
1303 historic estuarine sediments: a multidisciplinary approach. *Environment International*
1304 33(4), 436-444.
- 1305 Vis, G.J., Kasse, C., Vandenberghe, J., 2008. Late Pleistocene and Holocene palaeogeography of
1306 the Lower Tagus Valley (Portugal): effects of relative sea level, valley morphology and
1307 sediment supply. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 27, 1682-1709.
- 1308 Weistein, J.E., 1996. Anthropogenic impacts on salt marshes. In: Vernberg FJ, Vernberg WB,
1309 Siewicki T (eds) *Sustainable development in the southeastern coastal zone*. University
1310 of South Carolina Press, Columbia, SC, pp. 135-170.
- 1311 Weltje, G.J. von Eynatten, H., 2004. Quantitative provenance analysis of sediments: review and
1312 outlook. *Sedimentary Geology* 171(1-4), 1-11.
- 1313 Wu, Y., Hou, X., Cheng, X., Yao, S., Xia, W., Wang, S., 2007. Combining geochemical and
1314 statistical methods to distinguish anthropogenic source of metals in lacustrine sediment:
1315 A case study in Dongjiu Lake, Taihu Lake catchment, China. *Environmental Geology*
1316 52(8), 1467-1474.
- 1317 Zalasiewicz, J., Williams, M., Steffen, W., Crutzen, P., 2010. The New World of the
1318 Anthropocene. *Environmental Science and Technology* 44(7), 2228-2231.
- 1319 Zazo, C., Dabrio, C.J., Goy, J.L., Lario, J., Cabero, A., Silva, P.G., Bardají, T., Roquero, E.,
1320 2008. The coastal archives of the last 15 ka in the Atlantic-Mediterranean Spanish
1321 linkage area: Sea level and climate changes. *Quaternary International* 181 (1), 72-87.

- 1322 Zazo, C., Mercier, N., Silva, P.G., Dabrio, C.J., Goy, J.L., Roquero, E., Soler, V., de Luque, L.,
1323 2005. Landscape evolution and geodynamic controls in the Gulf of Cadiz (Huelva coast,
1324 SW Spain) during the Late Quaternary. *Geomorphology* 68 (3-4), 269-290.
- 1325 Zervas, D., Nichols, G.J., Hall, R., Smyth, H.R., Lüthje, C., Murtagh, F., 2009. SedLog: A
1326 shareware program for drawing graphic logs and log data manipulation. *Computers and*
1327 *Geosciences* 35(10), 2151-2159.
- 1328

Table 1.- Evaluation of the accuracy of element concentration measurements, involving calculation of the Relative Percentage Difference (RPD) and its comparison with certified values of the STSD-1 and STSD-2 Certified Reference Materials from stream sediments.

	% RPD	CAN STSD-1			CAN STSD-2		
		Obtained value	Certified value	% Recovered	Obtained value	Certified value	% Recovered
Al ₂ O ₃	0.30	8.67	9.00	96.3	16.0	16.1	99.4
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.33	6.28	6.50	96.6	7.35	7.50	98.0
MgO	0.04	2.16	2.20	98.2	3.15	3.10	102
CaO	0.01	3.66	3.60	102	4.18	4.00	105
Na ₂ O	0.32	1.73	1.80	96.1	1.70	1.70	100
K ₂ O	0.13	1.24	1.20	103	2.13	2.10	101
TiO ₂	0.01	0.64	0.80	80.0	0.73	0.80	91.3
MnO	0.00	0.47	0.50	94.0	0.13	0.10	130
TOT/C	0.05	13.2	12.3	108	1.69	1.60	106
As	0.28	19.8	23.0	86.1	33.3	42.0	79.3
Ba	0.45	585	630	92.9	515	540	95
Cd	0.05	0.90	<i>no data</i>	-	0.80	<i>no data</i>	-
Co	0.24	16.3	17.0	95.9	20.0	19.0	105
Cr	2.14	54.4	<i>no data</i>	-	102	<i>no data</i>	-
Cs	0.40	1.50	1.80	83.3	10.8	12.0	90.0
Cu	0.10	34.6	36.0	96.1	41.2	47.0	87.7
Ni	0.41	19.3	24.0	80.4	49.2	53.0	92.8
Pb	0.16	37.4	35.0	107	68.5	66.0	104
Rb	0.25	-	3.00	-	95.7	104	92
Sc	0.46	12.0	14.0	85.7	14.0	16.0	87.5
Sr	0.32	193	170	114	455	400	114
V	0.15	89.0	98.0	90.8	100	101.00	99.0
Y	0.20	36.2	42.0	86.2	35.6	37.0	96.2
Zn	0.04	150	178	84.3	193	246	78.5
Zr	0.25	221	218	101	183	185	99.1

Mayor in %, trace in ppm. % RPD (Relative Percentage Difference)

Table 2.- Summary information for ^{14}C age determinations showing conventional age, $\delta^{13}\text{C}\text{‰}$ 1σ range and midpoint. Radiocarbon ages were calibrated using the program CALIB v. 6.0 (Stuiver and Reimer 2009; Reimer et al. 2009).

Borehole n° sample	^{14}C Lab code	Depth cm	conv. ^{14}C age BP	$\delta^{13}\text{C}\text{‰}$ PDB	2σ range	midpoint cal. BP	Material	Method
CM1								
CM1.7	KIA-13241	787	3360±31	0.64	2984 - 3385	3185	<i>Cerastoderma glaucum</i>	AMS
CM1.1	GX-25447	824	5020±310	1.1	4509 - 6051	5280	<i>Cerastoderma glaucum</i>	b radiom.
CM1.2	GX-25448	1712	6210±220	-25.9	6626 - 7513	7070	peat	b radiom.
CM1.3	KIA-8376	1860	6205±40	2.08	6438 - 6836	6637	<i>Cerastoderma edule</i>	AMS
CM1.4	SAC-1534	2127	7590±100	0.02	7805 - 8312	8059	<i>Cerastoderma angulata</i>	b radiom.
CM1.5	GX-25449	2850	8430±380	1.5	8137 - 10009	9073	<i>Cerastoderma glaucum</i>	b radiom.
CM1.6	KIA-9691	3606	9500±70	na	10165 - 10545	10355	<i>Cerastoderma sp.</i>	AMS
CM2								
CM2.1	Beta-128887	200	3040±100	-27.3	2955 - 3449	3202	peat	b radiom.
CM2.2	Beta-128886	715	5980±160	0.4	5987 - 6782	6385	<i>Acanthocardia tuberculata</i>	b radiom.
CM3								
CM3.1	GX-25421	459	3300±160	25.9	2731 - 3538	3135	<i>Cerastoderma angulata</i>	b radiom.
CM3.2	GX-25452	960	6710±120	1.6	6897 - 7480	7189	<i>Cerastoderma angulata</i>	b radiom.
CM3.3	GX-25453	1452	7080±200	0.7	7159 - 7962	7561	<i>Cerastoderma angulata</i>	b radiom.
CM3.4	GX-25454	2690	9470±250	-22.9	10155 - 11412	10784	wood	b radiom.
CM5								
CM5.0	WK16012	333	3375±39	0.2	2994 - 3413	3204	<i>Scrobicularia plana</i>	AMS
CM5.1	KIA 15211	579	4295±35	na	4153 - 4625	4389	<i>Venerupis</i>	AMS
CM5.6	WK16013	890	6764±45	25.4	7115 - 7443	7279	<i>Cerastoderma glaucum</i>	AMS
CM5.2	KIA 15213	1085	4095±30	na	4027 - 4257	4142	<i>Cerastoderma edule</i>	AMS
CM5.3	KIA15212	1345	7585±35	na	7866 - 8202	8034	<i>Venerupis</i>	AMS
CM5.4	KIA15210	1775	7725±45	na	7999 - 8349	8174	<i>Cerastoderma.sp</i>	AMS
CM5.7	WK 16014	2095	8256±55	25.3	9083 - 9423	9253	wood	AMS
CM5.8	WK 16015	4270	10273±66	25.5	11802 - 12227	12015	wood	AMS
CM5.5	Beta-137110	4767	10990±40	-25.7	12681 - 12989	12835	wood	AMS
CM6								
CM6.1	CNA974	200	830 ± 30	-28.1	686 - 789	738	organic matter	AMS
CM6.2	CNA975	310	1000 ± 45	-31	792 - 981	887	organic matter	AMS
CM6.3	CNA976	450	1215 ± 35	30.6	1059 - 1189	1124	organic matter	AMS
CM6.4	KIA30369	1403	6060±50	-25.96	6777 - 7027	6902	peat	AMS
CM6.5	KIA30368	2120	7150±50	-8.36	7455 - 7789	7622	<i>Venus nux</i>	AMS
CM6.6	Beta-282088	5245	11110±40	-28.9	12792 - 13131	12961	wood	AMS
CM6.7	CNA979	5500	11370±50	-46.01	13125 - 13357	13241	organic matter	AMS

Table 3.- Descriptive statistics of the major and trace elements of the core sediments analysed. Major elements are reported in %, trace in ppm. PCC represents the Pearson correlation coefficient between designated variables (alpha significance level 0.05).

	CM5 CORE _{N=50}							CM6 CORE _{N=55}						
	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD	PCC SiO ₂	PCC Al ₂ O ₃	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD	PCC SiO ₂	PCC Al ₂ O ₃
Clay	19.0	18.4	3.73	38.9	5.51	-0.36	0.71	17.4	15.3	4.72	32.6	8.82	-0.38	0.92
Silt	74.6	76.2	15.3	80.5	8.91	-0.39	-0.16	68.5	70.3	34.4	81.2	9.53	-0.27	0.57
Sand	6.37	4.94	0.06	80.9	10.7	0.52	-0.23	14.1	12.7	0.01	58.4	15.3	0.39	-0.88
SiO₂	57.0	56.7	51.2	67.9	2.87	1.00	-0.44	58.3	58.2	34.5	75.7	6.53	1.00	-0.48
Al₂O₃	16.9	16.7	14.7	20.1	1.36	-0.44	1.00	15.0	14.9	7.1	19.9	3.25	-0.48	1.00
Fe₂O₃	6.34	6.19	4.45	11.1	0.99	-0.66	0.49	5.59	5.45	2.57	8.2	1.42	-0.46	0.89
MnO	0.06	0.05	0.03	0.43	0.06	-0.21	0.51	0.06	0.06	0.03	0.17	0.02	-0.08	0.15
MgO	1.80	1.82	1.35	2.06	0.13	-0.63	-0.05	1.74	1.79	0.67	2.15	0.27	-0.81	0.52
CaO	0.71	0.65	0.07	1.66	0.35	-0.21	-0.43	1.24	1.04	0.25	4.47	0.85	0.54	-0.84
Na₂O	2.05	2.16	1.39	2.64	0.37	0.07	-0.70	2.67	2.07	1.44	6.55	1.12	-0.36	-0.56
K₂O	2.87	2.82	2.50	3.50	0.24	-0.39	0.97	2.58	2.54	1.37	3.42	0.54	-0.40	0.98
TiO₂	0.89	0.90	0.79	1.00	0.05	0.41	0.02	0.86	0.88	0.32	1.07	0.14	-0.37	0.65
P₂O₅	0.13	0.12	0.06	0.33	0.04	-0.32	0.51	0.12	0.10	0.05	0.28	0.05	-0.31	0.79
LOI	11.3	11.0	4.90	15.5	1.93	-0.71	-0.23	11.8	10.9	4.60	38.6	4.99	-0.77	-0.16
TOT/C	1.42	1.44	0.14	2.23	0.43	-0.41	-0.49	2.22	1.57	0.62	13.8	2.03	-0.56	-0.38
TOT/S	0.77	0.78	0.03	1.62	0.48	-0.28	-0.60	0.74	0.73	0.08	2.03	0.55	-0.14	-0.55
As	14.8	15.3	1.00	24.7	4.15	-0.48	0.25	14.4	13.5	4.60	36.9	5.03	-0.47	0.55
Cd	0.09	0.10	< d.l.	0.30	0.05	0.04	-0.35	0.09	0.10	< d.l.	0.60	0.09	-0.58	-0.14
Co	16.3	15.7	11.5	28.7	3.17	-0.18	0.26	15.3	15.1	6.50	39.4	4.43	-0.33	0.60
Cr	21.8	22.4	17.6	25.6	2.10	-0.18	0.69	19.4	19.2	6.40	27.2	4.49	-0.64	0.92
Cu	26.9	25.7	16.5	42.1	4.78	-0.01	0.62	25.0	27.1	9.70	54.1	7.84	-0.82	0.67
Ni	32.7	31.5	24.9	60.7	5.80	-0.03	0.47	28.2	30.1	11.7	39.4	6.75	-0.59	0.92
Pb	18.3	17.9	13.9	35.6	3.76	-0.20	0.51	19.3	18.7	11.2	41.3	5.19	-0.52	0.41
Zn	71.7	70.0	55.0	88.0	7.55	-0.06	0.44	63.8	65.0	29.0	87.0	16.2	-0.43	0.95
Hg	0.53	0.52	0.02	3.19	0.56	0.10	-0.34	0.36	0.14	0.02	5.26	0.78	-0.22	0.08
Ba	407	397	351	477	35.5	-0.19	0.81	397	373	244	537	86.8	-0.31	0.95
Be	2.69	3.00	2.00	4.00	0.57	0.09	0.10	2.22	2.00	1.00	3.00	0.71	-0.41	0.74
Cs	7.64	7.80	5.10	9.50	0.90	-0.65	0.82	6.00	5.95	2.00	9.90	2.13	-0.44	0.98
Sc	16.3	16.0	14.0	20.0	1.31	-0.36	0.89	14.3	14.0	5.00	20.0	3.35	-0.63	0.96
Sr	116	115	93.0	144	9.64	-0.17	-0.23	136	129	101.7	216	25.7	0.52	-0.82
Th	13.5	13.4	10.9	16.9	1.17	-0.04	0.43	11.0	11.4	3.40	14.6	2.68	-0.50	0.90
U	3.86	3.70	2.90	8.20	0.99	-0.20	0.54	3.02	3.10	1.20	4.40	0.77	-0.59	0.83
V	120	120	100	151	11.8	-0.34	0.89	112	110	36.0	156	26.4	-0.67	0.94
Rb	127	125	108	165	12.9	-0.37	0.95	110	107	49.6	154	30.1	-0.43	0.99
Zr	218	206	165	315	38.1	0.58	-0.72	220	213	96.5	368	48.8	0.23	-0.09
Y	32.2	31.8	25.6	41.9	3.12	0.28	-0.14	30.2	30.7	11.4	41.6	6.20	-0.64	0.78

Table 4.- Statistics for element concentrations in the sedimentary units selected for calculation of natural background levels for the Guadiana River Estuary. Major elements are reported in %, trace in ppm.

	CM5 Core			CM6 Core			<i>Background</i>	<i>%RPD</i>
	Máx	Min	Mean	Máx	Min	Mean		
Al₂O₃	19.9	14.3	17.9	19.9	7.09	16.9	17.4	0.30
Fe₂O₃	8.22	4.70	6.64	8.22	2.57	6.16	6.40	0.33
MnO	0.11	0.04	0.06	0.11	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.01
TiO₂	1.01	0.85	0.9	1.01	0.32	0.86	0.89	0.00
As	22.8	7.70	14.7	36.9	9.30	16.9	15.8	0.28
Cd	0.10	0.01	0.09	0.10	0.01	0.08	0.09	0.05
Co	19.1	14.1	17.0	19.1	6.50	15.8	16.4	0.24
Cr	27.2	16.0	22.3	27.2	6.40	21.1	21.7	2.14
Cu	32.3	23.0	29.5	32.3	11.6	26.8	28.2	0.10
Ni	36.2	27.1	33.4	36.2	11.7	31.4	32.4	0.41
Pb	22.0	14.0	18.8	22.0	13.5	18.3	18.6	0.16
Zn	87.0	64.0	77.7	87.0	29.0	73.1	75.4	0.04
Ba	537	409	490	521	244	447	468	0.45
Rb	153	107	138	154	49.6	130	134	0.25
Sr	126	110	117	216	102	129	123	0.32
V	145	96.0	129	147	36.0	123	126	0.15
Y	36.9	33.9	35.7	36.9	11.4	32.3	34.0	0.20
Zr	339	182	235	339	96.5	214	224	0.25
Cs	9.60	5.70	7.81	9.90	2.00	7.54	7.67	0.40

Fig. 1. Maps of the study area, showing geological setting, locations of principal mining operations, and locations of the CM5 and CM6 cores in the Guadiana River Estuary.

Fig. 2. Aerial image showing the geographical context and location of the boreholes in the Guadiana saltmarshes system.

Fig. 3. Lithostratigraphic sequences of the CM5 and CM6 boreholes showing sedimentary units and their palaeoenvironmental significance based on textural features and the Foraminiferal Indicator of Marine Influence (FIMI). Pie-charts illustrate the structure of the foraminiferal assemblages in CM6. For every sedimentary unit 4 most representative were taken to compute average abundances, which are very similar to those described for CM5 (see Boski et al., 2008).

Fig. 4. Chronological model of the sedimentary infilling in the Guadiana Estuary (SW Iberia) showing the depth-age relationship in boreholes CM5 and CM6.

Fig. 5. Sea-level rise regression lines established from depth/age relations in 5 boreholes: CM6 this study, CM5 this study and Boski et al. (2008), CM1, CM2 and CM3 (Boski et al., 2002). The grey band shows the error margins of sea-level position, taking into consideration the uncertainties of ^{14}C dating and uncertainties of past sea-level determination with respect to the MSL.

Fig. 6. Results of factorial analysis (varimax rotation). Left-hand diagram shows variation in factor loadings for the elements studied in Guadiana cores CM5 and CM6; right-hand diagram shows variation with depth of the three main factors (F1, F2, and F3) for each core.

Fig. 7. Variation in Al and Sc with clay percentage in samples from Guadiana cores CM5 and CM6 (first graphic); relationship between aluminium and various metals in the samples (remainder of graphics). Regression lines and 95% confidence intervals are shown. Major elements are expressed in % and trace elements in ppm.

Fig. 8. Variation with depth of the Al_2O_3 -normalized concentrations of Fe, Mn, As, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb, and Zn through Guadiana cores CM5 and CM6. The synthetic sedimentary record and inferred natural processes or anthropogenic activities in the environment corresponding to the studied units are also shown.

Fig. 9. Vertical enrichment profiles (EF) for Fe, Mn, and trace metals in Guadiana cores CM5 and CM6, showing the behaviour of the elements in the prehistoric period.

Fig. 10. Relationship between geochemistry (Enrichment Factors) and possible changes induced by natural and/or anthropogenic agency in the Guadiana Estuary infill between the Holocene Period (more than 4500 years BP) and Anthropocene Period (4500 years BP to present, *sensu* Zalasiewicz et al., 2010). Palaeohistorical reconstruction based on both cores CM5 (11000 - 800 years BP) and CM6 (800 years BP–present). The figure shows the climate-optima after Dansgaard et al. (1969) and Schönwiese et al. (1995), as well as the most recent temperature and precipitation anomalies (TA and PpA, respectively) and social changes suggested by Büntgen et al. (2011).

Figure 1 colour

Figure 1-63

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 6

A: Neolithic B: Calcolitic, Cooper Age C: Bronze Age D: Iron Age E: Roman Period F: Post-Roman Period G: Modern Time

Figure 10

